

The role of Error Orientation and Innovation climate in the relationship between Psychological Safety and employee's entrepreneurial behavior

Applied to employees in outsourcing companies in Smart Village, Egypt.
A moderated-mediation analysis

By

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دور التوجه بالخطأ ومناخ الإبداع في العلاقة بين الأمان النفسي والسلوك الريادي للموظف
بالتطبيق على العاملين بشركات تعهيد الأعمال بالقرية الذكية بمصر

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ABSTRACT

Given the importance of the employees' role in intrapreneurship, this study aims to investigate employees' level factors that can positively affect employees' entrepreneurial behaviors (innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and work-related risk-taking). In particular, the study hypothesizes a moderated mediation model in which (a) psychological safety is directly and positively related to employees' entrepreneurial behaviors, (b) error orientations (error competence, learning from errors, error risk-taking, error communication, and thinking about errors) mediate the positive relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors, and (c) innovation climate within the organization strengthens the positive link between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors and the mediated link between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors via error orientations.

This study used a nonexperimental cross-sectional quantitative research method. The hypothesized model was tested using data collected from 379 full-time employees working at 34 ICT outsourcing companies in smart village, Egypt. Data were obtained using a self-report questionnaire collected via human resources management in the companies. The moderated mediation model was analyzed using path analysis employing a Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) macro named PROCESS.

The findings provided partial support for the moderated-mediation model, as well as it carried some unexpected results. The results of the study showed that psychological safety has a significant direct positive effect on all error orientations and on all employees' entrepreneurial behaviors. Considering the relationship between error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior; error competence, learning from errors, error risk-taking, and error communication positively affect employees' innovative behavior. Error risk-taking and error communication positively affect employees' proactive behavior and work-related risk-taking. But unexpectedly, the study found that thinking about errors negatively influences innovative behavior, and learning from errors negatively affects risk-taking.

Furthermore, through the results of the mediation hypothesis, it can be said that error risk-taking is the best explanation of the indirect relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors. Moreover, the innovation climate moderates the mediating effect of psychological safety on employees' entrepreneurial behavior via error risk-taking. The research concludes by discussing the results in more detail and discussing theoretical and practical implications.

Keywords: Psychological Safety; Error orientations; Innovation climate; Employees' entrepreneurial behaviors.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1. Background

1.1. Applied Background (Outsourcing in Egypt)

1.2. Theoretical Background

2. Research Gap

3. Research questions

4. Research Objectives

5. Research hypotheses

6. Summary of research methodology

7. Excepted outcomes and implications

8. Outline of the study

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Today's business environment is highly competitive and rapidly changing, which requires continuous improvements imperative to organizational success. Employees should participate in this improvement by adopting extra roles related to proactivity, creativity and innovation (Neessen, Caniëls, Vos, & De Jong, 2019). Hence the importance of entrepreneurial employees has been emphasized that employees' entrepreneurial behavior directly affects the firm's growth, direction, and strategic renewal (Blanka, 2019).

Employees' entrepreneurial behavior is defined as the extent to which individual workers proactively engage in creating, introducing, and applying opportunities at work marked by taking business-related risks (De Jong, Parker, Wennekers, & Wu, 2015). Entrepreneurial behaviors are searching for and developing ideas, networking behaviors, identifying opportunities and threats, nurturing ideas and marketing those to peers and management in the company, exerting effort to apply these ideas, and accepting the potential risks are entrepreneurial behavior (Afsar, Badir, Saeed, & Hafeez, 2017).

By nature, entrepreneurial behavior is a risky behavior because employees might have to deal with resistance from peers and managers throughout the process. Even after employees get the needed resources to implement their innovative ideas, they might face the risks of failure that may lead to reputation damage and even job loss. Therefore, prior research attempted to identify factors that foster employees' willingness to take risks and invest their energies into work. Remarkably, one cognitive state that has emerged as a key factor in facilitating the process of learning and innovation is psychological safety. It is defined as "the belief that the workplace is safe for interpersonal risk-taking" (Edmondson, 1999; Frazier, Fainshmidt, Klinger, Pezeshkan, & Vracheva, 2017; Kahn, 1990). Minimizing interpersonal risks in the workplace encourages employees to engage in risky behavior like creativity, innovation (Newman, Donohue, & Eva, 2017), and entrepreneurial behavior.

Furthermore, the research aims to shed light on the causal mechanisms underlying the relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior by examining positive orientations toward errors as a mediator. Error orientation reflects an individual's

beliefs, feelings, and behavioral tendencies towards errors; either he/ she considers errors threats or learning opportunities (Rybowiak, Garst, Frese, & Batinic, 1999). Entrepreneurship is employed in a complex environment and an uncertain context (Frese, 2009). Entrepreneurs face situational factors such as high novelty, time pressure, information overload, dealing with new products, services, etc. (Frese, 2009; Petkova, 2009). In such circumstances, it is more likely that errors will occur. Thus, dealing positively with errors and learning from them become vital for entrepreneurs. Therefore, employees need to be willing to risk making errors and mistakes in order to engage in entrepreneurial behaviors. To nurture a positive error orientation, employees need to feel that errors will not be taken against them, and they will be given the benefit of the doubt (Edmondson, Kramer, & Cook, 2004). Thus, the current study expects that error orientation plays a mediating role in the association between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior.

To ensure that psychological safety and error orientation results in entrepreneurial behavior, innovation climate -the norms and values inside an organization that enhances creativity and innovation- plays a critical role (Dhar, 2015). Innovation climate refers to employees' perception of the degree to which an organization supports and encourages employees to take the initiative to explore creative ideas that foster creativity within the organization (Agnihotri, Yang, & Briggs, 2019; Chan & Liu, 2012; Chan, Liu, & Fellows, 2014).

This chapter covers the background for the study, paving the way to define the research gap and then determine the research questions, objectives, and hypotheses. Finally, the chapter presents the outline of the study.

1. Background and context:

1.1. Applied Background (Outsourcing in Egypt):

Egyptian business process outsourcing (BPO) industry has largely contributed to the rapid growth of the country's economy. According to a report prepared in cooperation between the German Outsourcing Association and the IT Industry Development Agency

(ITIDA)¹, Egypt's overall IT (includes BPO) revenues are increased to \$4.28 billion in 2018 and reached \$5.5 billion in 2020, growing at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 13%. Precisely, the outsourcing sector – providing IT and ICT services from Egypt to international customers – is expected to remain strong over the coming years. Egypt's business process outsourcing market is particularly healthy, estimated at \$2 billion in 2017, expanding to approximately \$3.14 billion by the end of 2020 at CAGR 16.3% to be one the most significant contributors to IT growth by 2020 in Egypt.

This report was cited that Egypt enjoys a unique blend of qualities, making it one of the most attractive destinations for information technology and business process services globally. For instance, its location in the center of the world, cultural compatibility, physical proximity, similar time zone to the region facilitates productive business interactions, and specifically the talented and low-cost workforce. Additionally, multinational corporations operating in Egypt praise the high levels of quality and innovation of employees in service delivery and the ability to develop new initiatives for creating value for the business. Propped by its unique talents, the IT innovation arena in Egypt is flourishing, with several success stories of small companies securing millions of dollars of investments from Europe, the US, and the Middle East and successfully offshoring IT services to Europe, Middle East, and Africa.

Accordingly, the current study is motivated to focus on business process outsourcing companies in Smart Village², Egypt. The Smart Village was established in Egypt in 2001 to be the nucleus for building and growing the information technology industry in Egypt. Currently, it is the largest-gated business community in Egypt that accommodates Multinational and Local companies, Governmental, Financial Authorities, Organizations and Educational Institutions and Research & Development centers offering full-fledged services.

1.2. Theoretical Background:

Because of intrapreneurship's strategic importance, not only for organizations but also for social, sustainable, and economic development (Aparicio, Turro, & Noguera,

¹ Outsourcing Destination Guide-Egypt <https://eubis.org/outsourcing-destination-guide-egypt/>

² <https://www.smart-villages.com/about-smart-village/>

2020), various studies have been conducted on intrapreneurship from different theoretical perspectives. Basically, the studies have differentiated between intrapreneurship and entrepreneurship (Antoncic & Hisrich, 2003; Baruah & Ward, 2015; Camelo-Ordaz, Fernández-Alles, Ruiz-Navarro, & Sousa-Ginel, 2012; Molina & Callahan, 2009), showing that intrapreneurship has the same spirit of entrepreneurship but in a different context which is organization.

This broad view of intrapreneurship leads to diversity, differences, and sometimes confusion and overlap between entrepreneurial concepts explored in organizations. This study is considered intrapreneurship as a multilevel construction that starts from individual employee behaviors and ends with achieving intrapreneurial outcomes at the organizational level such as new product, new business venturing, or self-renewal (Neessen et al., 2019). From this view, intrapreneurship differs from corporate entrepreneurship, which focuses on the organizational level. And it differs from entrepreneurial orientation, which reflects top management orientation.

At the individual level, two concepts should be distinguished: entrepreneurial behavior and intrapreneurial behavior. Entrepreneurial behavior measures the employee's innovative, proactive, and risk-taking behavior regardless of the extent to which these behaviors contribute to the firm level. While intrapreneurial behavior measures the individual's activities that contribute to firm-level intrapreneurship, such as venture behavior and strategic renewal behavior (De Jong et al., 2015; Gawke, Gorgievski, & Bakker, 2019).

The scope of the present study is the employee's entrepreneurial behavior. More specifically, what motivates employees to participate in such entrepreneurial behaviors? Previous studies have investigated many organizational factors (e.g. organizational structures, processes and support) (Blanka, 2019) and individual factors (e.g. commitment, belongingness, satisfaction, self-efficacy, experience and personal knowledge) (Neessen et al., 2019) that influence entrepreneurial behavior. The current study is interested in examining psychological safety as an antecedent of employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

Psychological safety reduces perceived risks in the workplace. Consequently, it promotes risky behaviors (Agarwal & Farndale, 2017; Edmondson, 1999b; Leung, Deng,

Wang, & Zhou, 2015; Newman et al., 2017). Previous studies found a relationship between psychological safety and outcomes such as **creativity** (e.g., Agarwal & Farndale, 2017; Carmeli, Reiter-Palmon, & Ziv, 2010; Yang, Li, Liang, & Zhang, 2019), **innovation** (e.g., Baer & Frese, 2003; Zhu, Yao, & Zhang, 2019) at organizational and team level. Thus, psychological safety is expected to affect employees' entrepreneurial behavior at the individual level.

Furthermore, the study aims to understand the indirect relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior by testing the mediating role of error orientation. Psychological safety reduces the negative consequences related to errors like losing respect, feeling humiliated, or embarrassed because individuals believe they will be given the benefit of the doubt (Edmondson, 2004; Edmondson, Kramer, & Cook, 2004; Edmondson & Lei, 2014). Psychological safety facilitates failure-based learning behaviors (Carmeli, 2007; Carmeli & Gittell, 2009) and promotes employees' learning from errors (Ye, Wang, & Li, 2019). Consequently, psychological safety is expected to support employees to adopt positive orientations toward errors like error competence, error risk-taking, thinking about errors, and error communication. Indeed, errors play an important role in the entrepreneurial learning process because errors alert entrepreneurs of incorrect assumptions and beliefs and start a process of elaborate analysis that leads to the development of new knowledge (Petkova, 2009).

The study further investigates the moderating role of innovation climate as a facilitator of the interaction between psychological safety, error orientation, and intrapreneurial behavior. Previous studies support the argument that innovation climate is needed for encouraging creativity and innovation (e.g., Popa, Soto-Acosta, & Martinez-Conesa, 2017; Zhang et al., 2018; Shanker, Bhanugopan, Van der Heijden, & Farrell, 2017; Sönmez & Yıldırım, 2018; Zuraik & Kelly, 2019; Krufft et al., 2018; Liu, Chow, Zhang, & Huang, 2019). Innovation climate has been examined as a moderator that fosters employees' creativity and innovation behavior (e.g., Oke et al., 2013; Zhou, Zhang, & Alexandru, 2017). As such, it is expected that innovation climate strengthens the relationship between psychological safety, error orientation, and intrapreneurial behavior because it is non-

threatening psychologically, supports risk-taking and motivates the employees to apply initiative (Sönmez & Yıldırım, 2018).

2. Research Gap:

Based on the previous background, it can be captured that previous studies highly recommended study intrapreneurship at the individual level. Ireland, Covin, and Kuratko (2009) mentioned that behaviors and processes at the individual level are essential for any corporate entrepreneurship strategy. Miller (2011) also recommends studying the content of corporate entrepreneurship at other levels. The individual entrepreneurial activity represents an alternative type of entrepreneurship that expand corporate entrepreneurship studies and should focus on it in official statistics (de Jong, Parker, Wennekers, & Wu, 2015).

In a systematic literature review, Blanka (2019) argued that intrapreneurship is an emerging research field, especially at the employee level. Previous studies looked at employee entrepreneurship as a matter of choice between employment or entrepreneurship but have overlooked the case in which employees behave entrepreneurially within a corporate context. Thus, researchers should narrowly emphasize the individual factors of intrapreneurship (Blanka, 2019). Likewise, Neessen et al. (2019) recommended studying the attitudes and characteristics of the employee that influence intrapreneurial behavior.

At the individual level, although the extant literature has some studies that examined the effect of psychological safety on innovation, no studies were conducted to investigate the direct effect of psychological safety on employees' entrepreneurial behavior. Also, this is the first study that examine the direct effect of psychological safety on error orientation and the direct effect of error orientation on employees' entrepreneurial behavior. Moreover, the study explored the indirect relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior via error orientation as a mediator and innovation climate as a moderator.

Furthermore, the study extends existing research by exploring innovation climate as a moderator that strengthens the mediating role of error orientation in the relationships between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior. The researcher hypothesizes

that the indirect relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior via error orientation depends on the extent to which individuals perceive organizational support for creativity and innovation. Individuals who perform in a high innovation climate are more likely to feel psychological safety, develop positive attitudes toward errors, and behave entrepreneurially.

Therefore, based on the above explanation, the study contributes to the body of knowledge by filling the previous gaps. It represents the first study that examines these relationships, which researchers did not cover.

3. Research questions:

To increase the understanding of the individual-level factors that promoted employee's entrepreneurial behavior, the following questions are asked:

RQ1: What is the direct relationship between psychological safety, error orientation, and employees' entrepreneurial behavior?

RQ2: Which error orientations explain the indirect relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior?

RQ3: Does innovation climate moderate the relationship between psychological safety, error orientation, and employees' entrepreneurial behavior?

4. Research objectives:

Accordingly, this research has three main objectives. **First**, examining the effect of psychological safety on employees' entrepreneurial behavior. **Second**, understand the causal mechanisms underlying the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior by examining error risk taking as a mediator. **Third**, testing the moderating role of innovation climate. Achieving previous objectives would help the organization increase innovation, proactivity, and employee risk-taking, which contribute directly to the Egyptian sustainable development goals 2030, precisely the ninth goal about fostering innovation and entrepreneurship.

5. Research hypotheses:

To answer research questions, in the light of previous studies, this research hypothesizes the following:

H1: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H1a: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' innovative behavior.

H1b: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' proactive behavior.

H1c: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' risk-taking.

H2: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error orientation.

H2a: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error competence.

H2b: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on learning from errors.

H2c: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error risk-taking.

H2d: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on Error communication.

H2e: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on thinking about errors.

H3: Error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H3a: Error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' innovative behavior.

H3b: Error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' proactive behavior.

H3c: Error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' risk-taking.

H4: Error orientations mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H4a: Error orientations mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' innovative behavior.

H4b: Error orientations mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' proactive behavior.

H4c: Error orientations mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' risk-taking.

H5: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H5a: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' innovative behavior.

H5b: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' proactive behavior.

H5c: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' risk-taking.

H6: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H6a: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' innovative behavior.

H6b: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' proactive behavior.

H6c: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' risk-taking.

H7: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior via error orientations.

H7a: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior via error orientations.

H7b: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and proactive behavior via error orientations.

H7c: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and risk taking via error orientations.

6. Research methods:

A post-positivist philosophy has been adopted, which symbolizes the thinking after positivism, challenging the traditional view of the absolute knowledge truth. It needs the adoption of a deductive approach which necessitates the hypotheses development based on the adequate theoretical framework.

A quantitative method is used to realize the research findings. Data were collected using a questionnaire translated from English into Arabic. Preexisting measurement with established validity and reliability were used to measure the study variables. The sample

frame consisted of 8664 employees distributed over 34 companies. According to Saunders et al. (2016), at a 95% confidence level and an error margin of 5%, the sample should be 384 employees. This study utilized a simple random sample in proportion to the size of each company.

7. Excepted outcomes and implications

In addition to the significance of theory and knowledge gap, several practical implications can be derived from excepted findings. It is practically important for leaders to understand what fosters entrepreneurial behavior among employees. The researcher expects that employees with high psychological safety display entrepreneurial behavior more frequently under the roles of error orientation. Entrepreneurial employees can learn from past events and errors and thus increase their innovation, proactivity and risk-taking. Also, companies can foster these relationships through a heterogeneous innovation climate.

8. Outline of the study

Chapter one: Introduction

This chapter covers the background for the study paving the way to define the research gap, then determining problem statements, research questions, objectives, and hypotheses of the study. Finally, the excepted outcomes and the outline of the study.

Chapter two: Literature Review

This chapter outlines the literature review of the study variables. Initially, the literature of psychological safety, error orientation, intrapreneurial behavior and innovation climate. Finally, the relationships among study variables are examined to develop research hypotheses.

Chapter three: Research Methodology

This chapter outlines the research philosophy, approach, and research methods employed in the study. Moreover, the issues concerning the type of data, data collection techniques, and the time horizon of data collection are also discussed. Also, this chapter explained the questionnaire design, layout, and measures of the study constructs. Sampling issues related to population and sample, sampling unit, frame, size, and techniques are also revealed. Finally, the chapter addressed the stages used to perform questionnaire pilot

testing. Additionally, questionnaire validity and reliability as well as the procedures employed to translate the questionnaire, are also discussed.

Chapter Four: Data Analysis and Results

Firstly, this chapter analyzed the sample characteristics and the questionnaire response rate. Secondly, the chapter also outlined the results of the statistical analysis. Finally, the conclusions from statistical analysis are drawn.

Chapter five: Discussion, Conclusion, and Future research

This chapter involves the discussion concerning the hypotheses in the light of statistical analysis results as well as a conclusion for the whole study. Additionally, the theoretical and practical implications of the study are presented. Finally, study limitations, as well as suggestions for future research, are provided.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Psychological Safety

- 1.1. The concept of psychological safety
- 1.2. Psychological safety and other related concepts

2. Error Orientation

- 2.1. The concept of Error
- 2.2. The concept of Error Orientation
- 2.3. Error Orientation facets (dimensions)
 - 2.3.1. Error competences
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3. Employees' entrepreneurial behaviors

- 3.1. Intrapreneurship
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 - 3.4.1. Innovative behavior
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4. Innovation climate

- 4.1. Organizational climate and psychological climate
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5. Theoretical background and hypotheses:

- 5.1. Psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior
- 5.2. Psychological safety and error orientations
- 5.3. Error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior
- 5.4. The mediating role of error orientations
- 5.5. Innovation climate as a moderator

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter discusses the literature review of the research variables: Psychological safety, error orientation, entrepreneurial behavior, and innovation climate. Besides, the literature review will be utilized to develop the conceptual framework and research hypotheses.

1. Psychological Safety:

Psychological safety has evolved over time, from general to a specific concept. In 1954, Maslow described safety needs by some characteristics include “security; stability; dependency; protection; freedom from fear, anxiety, and chaos; the need for structure, order, law, limits; strength in the protector; and so on”. Maslow divided the need for safety into five categories: physical safety, material safety, inner safety, feeling safe around others, and feeling safe to others (Maslow, 1954). This primary view of safety includes both physical and psychological aspects, whereas the last three elements are psychological elements.

Depending on this general view, Schein and Bennis (1965) focused more on safety as a psychological construct. They discussed its critical role in the “unfreezing” process required for organizational learning and change. They explained it as the extent to which people feel confident and secure about managing change. They proposed that psychological safety reduces perceived threats, removes barriers to change, and creates a context that “encourages provisional tries and tolerates failure without retaliation, renunciation, or guilt (Frazier et al., 2017). Schein and Bennis (1965) did not give a specific definition of psychological safety but a generally accepted concept. But also, they allow other researchers to explore psychological safety as a freestanding concept in management and organizational research as follows:

1.1. The concept of psychological safety:

More specifically to the psychological aspects of safety and within the organizational behavior literature, Kahn (1990) defined psychological safety as one’s perception that he can express and apply his true self, and do not worry about any negative effects on his self-image, status, or career, because people assume that they will be given

the benefit of the doubt. Kahn's definition adds to the concept of psychological safety. He was more specific in defining what "fear" people try to overcome to be psychologically safe, as being afraid of the potential consequences of their behaviors and actions.

Moreover, Kahn (1990) determined four factors that affected psychological safety: First ongoing interpersonal relationships that provide supportiveness, mutual trust, understanding personality differences, and positive criticism. Second, group and intergroup dynamics evolved from group informal and unconscious roles. Third, Supportive, resilient, and clarifying management style and process. Finally, shared organizational norms set safety boundaries for member behaviors and emotions. So that, psychological safety is enhanced by the social system that creates more predictable, consistent, and non-threatening situations.

Considering Khan's four social factors, Edmondson (1999a) treated psychological safety as a team-level construct and defined it as a "shared belief among team members that it is safe to take interpersonal risks". Edmondson considered this belief generally implied and not pronounced by individuals or the team. Even though it is explicitly discussed in the team, the core of team psychological safety does not change. Further, he illustrated that psychological safety is a perception of the teamwork environment, where the team members will not embarrass, reject, or punish someone for being himself even if he makes some mistakes or speaks up about difficult issues (Edmondson, 1999b). So, in a psychological safety environment, people do not need to pretend or attitudinize anything to be accepted by others; instead, they feel accepted as themselves.

Edmondson's definition considers psychological safety comes from the perceptions of the entire team, not only the individual's perception about the relationship between him and the other employees or supervisors. From this point, Edmondson's definition is divergent from Kahn's definition, in which psychological safety is a perception emanating from the individual, not from the team.

Building on the previous essential work, many researchers explored psychological safety and adapted it according to the nature of their own studies. For example, Tynan (2005) looks at psychological safety from subordinate perceptions about his hierarchical relationship with his supervisor. She argued that psychological safety consists of two

connected constructs: “self-psychological safety”, which is considered a person evaluation of his feeling with a particular person (his supervisor in Tynan’s work). For example, a person feels psychologically safe if he thinks that his supervisor cares about him, works for his best interest, likes him as a person, and respects his abilities. The second construct is “other psychological safety”, a personal evaluation of another person’s feelings. For example, a person perceives his supervisor as psychologically safe if this supervisor accepts criticism, tries to understand when someone disagreed with him, does not ask to support his ideas, and is not overly sensitive.

Moreover, Tynan emphasizes the importance of studying both aspects. Because people, even if they feel psychologically safe, they are affected by their perceptions about other psychological safety. Simply, they think it is unsafe for others to take interpersonal risks. For instance, an employee has something to say and feels that there are no negative consequences on him. In this case, it is expected that employee feels psychological safety and he will speak up. But suppose he thinks that his supervisor will not be happy or feel embarrassed; accordingly, he may hold his words to save his interpersonal relationship with his supervisor. He stays silent due to the low-level other psychological safety, not his self-psychological safety.

Despite the outward difference between these definitions and different levels of analysis, they are all integral views of the same construct. They all converge around a single, unifying principle: the importance of reducing the perceptions of interpersonal risk in the workplace to facilitate the willing contribution of ideas and actions to a shared enterprise (Edmondson & Lei, 2014; Frazier et al., 2017). But studies captured it differently according to the level of analysis. At the organizational level, psychological safety is captured as an organizational climate evaluated by managers (e.g., Andersson, Moen, & Brett, 2020; Baer & Frese, 2003). At the team level, psychological safety represents the shared belief about interpersonal risk among team members, evaluated by the team leader (e.g., Gu, Wang, & Wang, 2013) or the aggregated opinion of team members (e.g., Post, 2012; Zhu, Yao, & Zhang, 2019). This study interested in psychological safety at the individual level, considering it as the employees' personal evaluation of his/her willingness to take interpersonal risks in the workplace. Based on this, the next point discusses the

difference between psychological safety and other related concepts to prevent confusion and clarify what is specifically meant by psychological safety.

1.2. Psychological safety and other related concepts:

Psychological safety demonstrates a special cognitive state different from other related states studied in organizational research like psychological empowerment and trust. Firstly, psychological empowerment is a core motivational state that describes employees' sense of control over their tasks, depending on four cognitions: a sense of meaning, competence, impact, and self-determination. So, it focuses on the feeling about specific jobs or tasks, while Psychological safety focuses on perceptions about interpersonal relationships in the social and work environment (Frazier et al., 2017; Spreitzer, 1995).

Moreover, psychological safety explains the interpersonal consequences of behaviors, while psychological empowerment tries to understand the intrapersonal influence within a role. Consequently, the type, quality, and nature of the interpersonal relationships people form with others will affect power realization in the workplace. And feeling safe enables individuals to pursue personally meaningful values, goals, and ideas without fear of negative consequences. As a result, psychological safety is positively associated with each empowerment cognition (Jha, 2019; Simonet, Narayan, & Nelson, 2014).

The second related state is trust, most trust definitions revolve around willing vulnerability, as the trustor expect that another specific person is trustworthy as this person will act in a beneficial way to the trustor regardless of the ability to monitor or control that person (Edmondson, 2003; Edmondson, Kramer, & Cook, 2004; Mayer, Davis, & Schoorman, 1995). So, it is the trustor decision to trust someone.

Comparing both concepts, psychological safety and trust, they both describe psychological states involving perceptions of risk or vulnerability, as well as making choices to minimize negative consequences (Edmondson, 2003; Edmondson et al., 2004; Maximo, Stander, & Coxen, 2019; Triplett & Loh, 2017). But the nature of this vulnerability is more narrowly defined for psychological safety than for trust (Edmondson, 2003).

Furthermore, Edmondson (2003) determined three elements of psychological safety that distinguishes it from trust (Edmondson, 2003; Edmondson et al., 2004; Frazier et al., 2017; Maximo et al., 2019; Triplett & Loh, 2017) (see Table 2/1). First, the timeframe, trusting someone takes a relatively long time and affects the trustor into the distant future. On the other hand, psychological safety is considered very short-term interpersonal consequences. Second, the object of focus, trust focuses on other people's actions; if these actions are in his favor, they can be trusted and given the benefit of the doubt. In contrast, psychological safety focuses on the actions of the person himself and whether others give him the benefit of the doubt on these actions, or it will be taken against him and interpreted in bad faith. Third, levels of analysis, trust primarily described a dyadic relationship, a feeling toward a specific person. In comparison, psychological safety is mostly acclimated by ongoing interpersonal interactions among close coworkers.

Table (2-1):

A comparison between psychological safety and trust.

	Trust	psychological safety
	<p>Person feels psychological safety → others gave him the benefit of the doubt</p>	
Focus	External Others' potential actions	Internal Person's actions
Time frame	Long term consequences	Short term consequences
Level of analysis	Specific dyadic relationship	Interpersonal interactions among close coworkers

Adapted from Edmondson, 2003 and Edmondson et al., 2004

It may be said that the third difference is only from Edmondson perspective as she treated psychological safety as a team level construct. But this is not true because if we want to evaluate the psychological safety of one person among five coworkers, and he thinks that if he asks a question, only one person of five may laugh at him, we can't say he

feels psychological safety. In short, psychological safety is a perception that grows in “oneself” from interpersonal interactions with “many others”.

Moreover, Kahn (1990) argues that interpersonal relationships characterized by trust promote psychological safety. More follower studies showed that trust had a significant positive effect on psychological safety; For example, May, Gilson and Harter (2004) found that trustworthy supervisory behaviors and affective trust-building co-worker relations motivate psychological safety. Li & Tan (2013) argue that trust decreases the perceived uncertainty and threats inherent in the social context, leading to less interpersonal risk in the workplace, thus strengthening employees’ psychological safety.

2. Error Orientation:

Working is a behavior to achieve certain goals. Errors are considered avoidable negative deviations from those goals (Zhao & Olivera, 2006). So, it is primarily perceived as unfavorable events for individuals as they cause stress, embarrassment, or shame. Also, for organizations, errors lead to inflation in tasks time more than planned, reflected in economic costs increase, spread negative impressions and reputations, and negatively affects customer satisfaction (Lauzier & Mercier, 2017; Zhao & Olivera, 2006). Subsequently, many attempts are made to prevent errors from happening or minimize their effects, though errors are still inescapable. Alternatively, errors should be treated as a chance to learn and take lessons for the future; this is the value of errors.

2.1. The concept of error:

Assuming that human behavior is goal-oriented, Zhao and Olivera (2006) defined errors as individuals' decisions and behaviors that cause an unwanted gap between a desired and actual state and result in negative outcomes that could have been prevented (Zhao, 2011; Zhao & Olivera, 2006; Hetzner, Gartmeier, Heid, & Gruber, 2011). This gap may occur due to a previous error in perception, thinking or any stage of human action. And conflict with internal or external norms and standards (Rausch, Seifried, & Harteis, 2017).

Furthermore, Bauer (2008) investigate errors as an antecedent of learning and conceptualize it as individual behavior that risks achieving lower or higher-order goals; this behavior may be decisions or just omissions. It is important to recognize erroneous action from its consequence. Defining errors focus on the mistaken action, whether it leads to negative results or not. The work environment may be strong enough to help detect and correct the errors before noticeable negative effects appear. In this case, there is still an error (Bauer, 2008).

Moreover, Errors are emotional events (Zhao, 2011); because determining the erroneous action requires external performance reviews, this may produce negative emotions such as shame, guilt, anger, fear of “losing face”, and so forth (Rausch et al., 2017). This was mentioned because negative emotions resulting from errors affect how people deal with them (Rausch et al., 2017).

Errors are normative or relativity concepts because they are subject to normative criteria, differing according to socio-cultural contexts. Therefore, errors should be evaluated by experts of the particular work domain under examination (Bauer, 2008). Hence, there is no objective feature to consider an error but depends upon norms and criteria applied in a specific environment. For example, arriving 30 min late for a scheduled meeting is regarded as an error in a bureaucratic culture, but maybe not in a more flexible, entrepreneurial workplace environment (Hetzner et al., 2011).

Errors are different from other concepts, leading to similar negative consequences such as failure, violation, and risk. Failure is defined broader than errors, as deviation from expected and desired results, including avoidable and unavoidable negative outcomes of experiments and risk-taking (Cannon & Edmondson, 2001, 2005). According to other factors in the work environment, errors may lead to failures or not. For example, prescribing the wrong drug to a patient (the error) may or may not cause bigger negative effects (failure) depending on other factors like the patient health condition or other medication that might interact with the wrong drug (Frese & Keith, 2015).

Compared to violations, violations include the intention to break a rule or be non-compliance with standards, while errors are unintentional deviations from goals, rules, and standards. Errors are also differentiated from risks. Risks refer to the environment being unsafe or unstable, and it is possible to suffer, lose, or fail to reach the goal. In contrast, errors refer to acts committed by humans or through the interaction of individuals with the environment in an unpredictable way (Frese & Keith, 2015; Lei, Naveh, & Novikov, 2016).

This study examine errors on the individual level caused by the individual's actions without participation by other individuals (Lei et al., 2016) since the study aims to investigate individuals attitudes toward their errors.

2.2. The concept of error orientation:

The concept of error orientation introduced by Rybowskiak et al. (1999) focuses on evaluating an individual's beliefs, feelings, and behavioral tendencies towards errors, whether he considers errors threats or learning opportunities. Error orientation is a general concept that evaluates two reactions when committing an error: firstly, the emotional reactions concerning how negatively perceiving errors in the first place, and the extent of

openness to dealing with errors. Secondly, the behavior reactions represented in the coping strategies in the face of errors. On the one hand, denying and covering up the errors, on the other hand, communicating and asking for advice to learn from them (Rausch et al., 2017; Rybowskiak et al., 1999).

Depending on Rybowskiak et al. (1999) essential work, many following studies explain the concept of error orientation as a personal disposition related to one's mentality during errors situations (Arenas, Taberero, & Briones, 2006). Error orientation is the individual's reaction when his action deviates from the desired goal (Weiwei & Xiaodong, 2010), and his attitude and behavior in processing and dealing with that error (Schell & Conte, 2008), also his beliefs about stress, anticipation, or learning accompanying the errors (Lauzier & Mercier, 2017). Moreover, Wei and Hisrich (2016) defined error orientation as the individual's cognitive strategy used in error management and contains both emotions and actions to remedy the error.

2.3. Error Orientation facets (dimensions):

Rybowskiak et al. (1999) presented five positive facets of individual attitude towards errors as follows:

2.3.1. Error competence:

Error competence indicates that the person has active knowledge that enables him to recover immediately from errors and mitigate negative consequences (Rybowskiak et al., 1999)(Hetzner et al., 2011). Additionally, it reflects one's sense of efficacy to cope with errors in the short term (Schell & Conte, 2008).

Previous studies found that error competence related to self-efficacy, to action-orientation after failure, need for achievement, initiative (Rybowskiak et al., 1999), Constructive Controversy (Tjosvold & Yu, 2007), polychronic and learning goal orientation (Schell & Conte, 2008), reflection at work (Hetzner et al., 2011) and emotion control in error situation and feel contented and accepted (Rausch et al., 2017).

2.3.2. Learning from errors:

This orientation refers to the ability to take lessons from errors and benefit from it to change work processes to prevent errors recurrence in the future (Rybowskiak et al., 1999).

So, learning from errors describe long-term learning orientation reflected in justified improvements in work processes. This time frame differentiates learning from errors from error competence, which indicate the short-term orientation of coping with errors immediately (Rybowiak et al., 1999).

Building on a cognitive and an activity perspective on experiential learning, Bauer (2008) defined learning from errors at work as an intentional, goal-directed process of gaining new or change current knowledge and skills through the experience of personally relevant errors encountered during daily work, purposed to avoid perpetuating the same error in the future. Furthermore, Bauer (2008) defined learning from errors as “action-reflection-action” cycles. Learning from error begins with (1) having a *concrete experience* to recognize and acknowledge the occurrence of the error. (2) *Reflection* means performing root-cause analysis to specify error causes. Then, (3) develop new *action strategies*, including considering strategies to change the cause, proposing alternatives for future acting, allocating required information and resources, and planning the implementation. Finally, (4) *implementation and evaluation* of the new strategy. Accordingly, learning from errors has short-term effects (changes in knowledge) and long-term effects (changes in actions and practices).

Additionally, Bauer and Mulder (2013) framed the process of learning from errors as a self-organized effort to specify the causes of an error and to develop action strategies that aim to prevent errors in the future. Engagement in learning from errors activities requires initially to estimate of an error as relevant to learning; this estimation enhances engagement in social learning activities concerning the joint analysis of causes and the development of new action strategies (Bauer & Mulder, 2013; Leicher, Mulder, & Bauer, 2013; Leicher & Mulder, 2016).

Learning from errors was found to be positively related to change readiness, self-efficacy, the need for accomplishment and action orientation after failure (Rybowiak et al., 1999), reflection at work (Hetzner et al., 2011), entrepreneurial opportunity identification behavior, entrepreneurial decision making (Wei & Hisrich, 2016), motivation to learn and intention to transfer learning (Lauzier & Mercier, 2017).

2.3.3. Error risk-taking:

Rybowiak et al. (1999) provided two complementary theoretical explanations of error risk-taking. First, it expresses general flexibility and openness towards errors, making individuals ready to adapt to new work conditions and take responsibility regardless of errors. Second, it results from a high achievement-oriented attitude that drives individuals to accept errors occurrence to achieve higher goals. Moreover, Tjosvold and Yu (2007) defined error risk-taking as readiness to make decisions and take action to accomplish goals with the clear realization that errors and mistakes might be made.

There are positive relations between error risk-taking and readiness for change, initiative (Rybowiak et al., 1999), learning goal orientation (Arenas et al., 2006), engagement in reflective activities (Bauer, 2008), reflection at work (Hetzner et al., 2011), constructive controversy, manager ratings of the group's innovation and recovery from mistakes (Tjosvold & Yu, 2007).

2.3.4. Error communication:

Error communication determines the individual willingness to discuss their errors to rectify errors, improve error handling, ask for help or warn from making the same mistake in the future (Rybowiak et al., 1999). Error communication is an individual tendency to communicate errors openly and is positively correlated with feeling motivated and curious during error situations (Rausch et al., 2017). It assessed communication and openness to discuss errors and misinterpretations with peers (Tulis, 2013). And indicate resorting to colleagues and seeking help when made errors (König, Steinmetz, Frese, Rauch, & Wang, 2007).

Error communication is the opposite face of covering-up errors. Likewise, Error communication could be explained through cost-benefit analysis. Communicating about errors may imply considerable costs for individuals, such as costs of acquiring the right information about the error, costs of receiving negative information about the self, and costs of expressing the need for help. By communicating errors, individuals risk receiving negative assessments from their supervisors and peers, negatively affecting their self-esteem. So, individuals will only communicate errors if they feel that the perceived benefits outweigh the costs related to these behaviors (Chughtai & Buckley, 2010).

2.3.5. Thinking about errors:

Thinking about errors is considered an analytical review and evaluation of the error, which aims to understand how the error occurred, how to correct it and how to prevent it in the future (Rybowiak et al., 1999).

Consistent with these five facets, Farnese, Fida, and Picoco (2020) try to explain how these dimensions are reflected in theory, going beyond the positive-negative view adopted by many researchers they incorporating two complementary theoretical frameworks. First, they draw on the transactional stress framework, which is already used by Rybowiak et al. (1999), considering that errors are stressful events to cope with it. The stress framework has two processes: the appraisal of erroneous actions and the coping strategies (problem and emotion-focused behavioral strategies). Second, drawing on attitude theory, they depicted attitudes by cognitive, affective, and behavioral components. Table 2/2 presented a summary of the Farnese et al. (2020) integrated model.

Table (2-2):

Error Orientation by Adopting both the Attitude and Stress Frameworks:

		Attitude Framework	
		Cognitive	Behavioral
Stress Framework	Appraisal process	⇒ risk-taking	
	Coping process	⇒ learning	⇒ Thinking ⇒ Communication ⇒ Competence

Adapted from Farnese et al., (2020).

According to Farnese et al. (2020), every facet of error orientation has two theoretical dimensions to explain it. Accordingly, error risk-taking is a positive appraisal of errors, which means that individuals adopt a positive pre-evaluation about errors by expressing optimistic expectations. At the same time, error risk-taking is a cognitive facet that captures a positive “belief” about errors. While the remaining four faces (competence, learning, communication, and thinking) are problem-focused coping – not appraisal – strategies to manage errors as they reflect the individual's behavior after the errors occurred. Looking at these four dimensions according to the attitude framework, learning

from errors represents a cognitive facet that reflects the belief that errors are opportunities to learn. While competence, communication, and thinking are behavioral facets that reflect actions and behaviors that a person takes to deal with errors. For example, being willing to recover errors as soon as possible, asking for help, or analyzing errors.

The current study is concerned with the five aforementioned aspects. Since they are the most appropriate for the study purpose, these are the positive orientations, which are expected to lead to employee's entrepreneurial behavior in contrast to the negative orientations.

3. Employee's Entrepreneurial Behavior:

3.1. Intrapreneurship:

Pinchot (1985) introduced the term “intrapreneur,” a synthesis of “intracorporate” and “entrepreneur.” Intrapreneurs generate new ideas and apply them just like an entrepreneur but inside an organization. Pinchot describes intrapreneurship as innovative and revolutionary actions that break the status-quo and hierarchy in an organization. In this stage, researchers defined intrapreneurship in several ways, for instance, a process of exploiting the opportunities that individuals undertake within organizations beyond the resources currently available to them. It is doing something new and unusual to discover opportunities, a spirit of entrepreneurship within the operating organization. And it is the motivation of renewal and innovation within the organization to create a new organization by an existing organization or new venture formation. In 1992, the word ‘intrapreneur’ was added to The American Heritage Dictionary, which defining it as “a person within a large corporation who takes direct responsibility for turning an idea into a profitable finished product through assertive risk-taking and innovation” (Antoncic & Hisrich, 2001, 2003).

Intrapreneurship at this stage was defined as any entrepreneurial action inside existing organizations (Afriyie, Melyoki, & Nchimbi, 2020; Antoncic & Hisrich, 2001, 2003; Woo, 2018; Baruah and Ward 2015; Antoncic and Antoncic, 2011). That accepted broad definition is appropriate for early stages of concept development and gave a degree of freedom to theoretical and empirical research to address the concept from different perspectives, contributing to the understanding, classifying, and defining the concept as a whole (Antoncic & Hisrich, 2003). As intrapreneurship is closely associated with entrepreneurship, it is important to differentiate between them.

3.2. Intrapreneurship and Entrepreneurship:

Entrepreneurship definitions revolve around discovering, developing, and exploiting opportunities in forming a new company (Shane, 2003). It is a process of opportunity revelation and developing it to create value through innovation and seizing that opportunity regardless of the required resource and location of the entrepreneur (Antoncic & Antoncic, 2011). Entrepreneurship, at its core, is a positive motivation to challenge and

change the current situation by adapting to the changing environment with an innovative and creative mindset (Park, 2017).

Intrapreneurship has the same spirit as entrepreneurship. Thus, it should be viewed essentially as an activity-based concept. Accordingly, Antoncic and Hisrich (2001) defined it to include any innovative activities in operating organizations. For example, the development of new products, services, technologies, administrative techniques, strategies, and competitive postures and creating new business ventures. Furthermore, Antoncic and Hisrich (2003) considered it the behaviors and behavioral intentions to change the traditional way of working and take the existing organizational conditions into new directions. Also, they differentiate intrapreneurship from similar concepts such as diversification, capability, organizational learning, and organizational innovation

However, there is a difference in the context in which entrepreneurs and intrapreneurs carry out their activities. Unlike the free entrepreneur who creates an entirely new company, the intrapreneur acts within an existing organizational hierarchy. Intrapreneurs should generate new ideas and search for new opportunities appropriate to their organization (Camelo-Ordaz et al., 2012). Subsequently, there are some key differences between intrapreneurship and entrepreneurship:

First, *setting and context* as intrapreneurship is operated by employees inside an existing organization. Thus, intrapreneurs are more oriented to the internal organizational environment to get support. In contrast, entrepreneurship is externally oriented as entrepreneurs create a new organization that requires support from the external environment (Camelo-Ordaz et al., 2012; Molina & Callahan, 2009).

Second, *the sort and the amount of risk and resources*, entrepreneurs have to take all the risk and responsibility using their resources, while intrapreneurs take less risk as the company share them in risk and responsibilities and provide them with resources (Baruah & Ward, 2015; Molina & Callahan, 2009). However, intrapreneurs want to change the status quo, think in opportunities regardless of available resources, and ask for additional resources and support. If they fail to deliver the plan successfully, they put their career at risk (De Jong, Parker, Wennekers, & Wu, 2011). Thus, intrapreneurs take risks, but it is different from those that entrepreneurs take.

Third, *the amount of freedom and control*, entrepreneurs tend to develop implied knowledge in new organizations, contrasting to intrapreneurs who work within organizations that already mature unique politics, languages, procedures, and bureaucracy (Camelo-Ordaz et al., 2012; Molina & Callahan, 2009). Thus, entrepreneurs exercised much freedom and control over their work. But also, they have less access to this important organizational infrastructure.

Fourth, *the nature of the personal reward*, entrepreneurs benefit directly from their success, financially and non-financially. In comparison, intrapreneurs' reward depends on employment and organizational policy (Baruah & Ward, 2015). Hence, the rewards for intrapreneurs are limited compared to entrepreneurs.

As a result of recognizing that intrapreneurship occurs in existing organizations, it is necessary to differentiate it from other entrepreneurial concepts explored in the same context, which is existing organizations. So, the research proposes the following concept map.

3.3. A map for intrapreneurial/entrepreneurial concepts within organizations:

First of all, intrapreneurship is a special concept that differs from other organizational concepts such as organizational capabilities, organizational learning, and organizational innovation. Intrapreneurship is about emergence, creation, and newness, not about the product/market relatedness and synergy with the existing business at the corporate level like diversification strategy. Intrapreneurship focuses particularly on innovative capabilities, not on all organizational capabilities' coherence and synergies inside and outside the business. It may improve organizational routines and knowledge; it does not necessarily start from what already exists and does not essentially aim to build organizational memory and routines like organizational learning. Also, it covers additional elements over organizational innovation; the most important one is the new business venturing (Antoncic & Hisrich, 2003).

Until now, there is still confusion and overlap in the entrepreneurial concepts used in existing organizations, which makes reaching a specific definition of entrepreneurship at the employee level a matter that needs to pave the way first and requires a map to define it well. For example, Antoncic and Hisrich (2003) conceptualize intrapreneurship as an

organizational level construct. They consider intrapreneurship as an umbrella that includes entrepreneurial orientation and corporate entrepreneurship. In contrast, other studies, such as Åmo and Kolvereid (2005) and Rigtering and Weitzel (2013), consider intrapreneurship a bottom-up approach that starts from the individual level. So. It is not an organizational level construct. Additionally, in a systematic literature review, Neessen, Caniëls, Vos, & De Jong (2019) found that both terms ‘intrapreneurship’ and ‘corporate entrepreneurship’ are used mutually in definitions that emphasize the individual or the organization. Among 73 definitions, they found 37 considered both concepts from the organizational perspective, and 36 incorporated the individual perspective.

Even when considering intrapreneurship starts at the individual level, studies differ on how to measure it and how it contributes to outcomes at the organizational level. While Blanka (2019) considered intrapreneurship a purely individual level construct, captured by employees behaviors (e.g. innovative and proactive behavior) and ignored intrapreneurship role at the organizational level. Neessen, Caniëls, Vos, & De Jong (2019) argued that in addition to the individual nature of intrapreneurship which is captured through behaviors, it should be manifested in organizational outcomes (e.g. new product, new business venturing, and self-renewal). Neessen et al. (2019) capture these organizational outcomes at the overall firm level, not how each employee contributes by his behavior to achieve these outcomes. Recently, Gawke, Gorgievski and Bakker (2019) argued that it is useful to measure employee activities that contribute to firm-level intrapreneurship and know each employee behavior contributes to the organizational outcomes.

Based on the previous controversies, the current research proposes the following classification map of the concepts of intrapreneurship/entrepreneurship within organizations, shown in figure (2-1).

In the beginning, corporate entrepreneurship is different from intrapreneurship at the level of analysis. Corporate entrepreneurship is an organizational level construct that reflects activities initiated top-down by the organization, while intrapreneurship is an individual-level construct that reflects activities pursued bottom-up by employees within the organization (Rigtering & Weitzel, 2013).

Figure (2-1): A classification map of intrapreneurship/entrepreneurship concepts within organizations.

On the one hand, corporate entrepreneurship refers to formal or informal activities that create new businesses in established companies through product and process entrepreneurial innovations and market initiatives (Kuratko, 2017). It concerns building an atmosphere that affects the behavior of managers, employees, and other stakeholders in the organization to make them engaged in entrepreneurial actions that lead to firm-renewal and/or corporate venturing (Guerrero & Peña-Legazkue, 2013). Accordingly, corporate entrepreneurship requires top management to have an “*entrepreneurial orientation*” to achieve “*corporate venturing*” and “*strategic renewal*”.

Entrepreneurial orientation is defined as the strategic posture of the firm management towards entrepreneurship, seen through the decision-making practices, managerial philosophies, and strategic behaviors (Anderson, Kreiser, & Donald, 2015). The end results of entrepreneurial orientation - at the same organizational level - are shown through (1) corporate venturing, which is related to creating new ventures whether within the firm, outside of the firm, or by cooperation with another firm. Or through (2) strategic renewal, which indicates the large-scale innovations adopted by the firm to achieve a competitive advantage, these innovations may take place in the firm’s strategy, product

offerings, served markets, internal organization, or business model (Kuratko, 2017; Kuratko & Audretsch, 2013; Kuratko & Morris, 2018).

In their pursuit of corporate venturing and strategic renewal, entrepreneurship-oriented managers use employees. Corporate entrepreneurship is considered a request from entrepreneurial management to employees to take initiatives, employee entrepreneurial behavior, and share in accomplishing corporate venturing and strategic renewal (Åmo & Kolvereid, 2005).

On the other hand, intrapreneurship is considered an independent initiative from employees (Åmo & Kolvereid, 2005). Intrapreneurship is a process whereby employee(s) recognize and exploit opportunities by being innovative, proactive and by taking risks for the organization to create new products, processes, and services, initiate self-renewal or venture new businesses to enhance the competitiveness and performance of the organization (Neessen et al., 2019). The previous definition illustrates the multilevel nature of intrapreneurship as it consists of (1) employees' entrepreneurial behaviors (innovativeness, proactiveness, opportunity recognition and exploitation, risk-taking, and networking), which lead to (2) organizational intrapreneurial outcomes (new business venturing and strategic renewal).

Although corporate entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship are different in the starting point, they meet the end purpose of achieving new business venturing and strategic renewal. But according to the different nature of each of them, they view this end purpose differently. While corporate entrepreneurship measures new business venturing and strategic renewal at the organizational level, intrapreneurship measures employee activities and behaviors that contribute to new venture creation and strategic renewal, called intrapreneurial behaviors.

Hence, at the individual level, employees' entrepreneurial behavior is differentiated from employees' intrapreneurial behaviors according to what they measure. Employees' entrepreneurial behavior are the employees showing initiative taking calculated risks, and creating innovations for the organization. Measured by the employee's entrepreneurial orientation, such as risk-taking, proactive behavior, and innovative behavior. Employees'

intrapreneurial behavior is employees' agentic behavior that contribute to firm-level intrapreneurship, such as new venture creation and strategic renewal (Gawke et al., 2019).

3.4. Employees' entrepreneurial behaviors:

The broader scope of intrapreneurship refers to a bottom-up process that covers the individual level of employees' behaviors and how these behaviors contribute to the organization's strategic renewal and new ventures (Neessen et al., 2019; Woo, 2018). The scope of the present study is the first part of the previous definition; the study explore the individual-level aspects of intrapreneurship “employee’s entrepreneurial behaviors.”

Employee’s entrepreneurial behaviors refer to organizational employee initiatives to add something new for the business without being asked to do so (De Jong & Wennekers, 2008). It is a self-starter process of taking initiatives and changing the customary ways of doing things in the organization, using the organizational resources innovatively and proactively to increase the performance and competitiveness of this organization (Afriyie et al., 2020).

Definitions of employee entrepreneurship share several themes. First, an entrepreneurial employee is a proactive individual who has a strong desire for action. He is a ‘self-starter’s’ person to the extent that he may not even ask for permission and ignore the negative environmental reactions about his ideas. Second, he is a resourceful person. He focuses on seizing the opportunity regardless of the resources he controls. Third, he directs his efforts towards the new and innovative actions which deviate from the status quo (De Jong & Wennekers, 2008).

Definitions of individual-level entrepreneurship concentrate on describing behaviors and actions of the intrapreneurial employee (Neessen et al., 2019). Defining entrepreneurial behavior as the extent to which individuals proactively identify and exploit opportunities at the workplace accept taking business-related risks (Afsar, Badir, Saeed, & Hafeez, 2017; De Jong, Parker, Wennekers, & Wu, 2015).

According to the previous definitions of employee entrepreneurial behavior, as a bottom-up process of taking initiatives to implement new ideas and innovations in organization, considering taking related risks. This study identified three features of

intrapreneurial behavior to investigate: innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and risk-taking.

These three features are considered key defining elements of employees' entrepreneurial behavior. Because of (1) Innovative behavior includes the behavioral elements required in intrapreneurship, such as recognizing opportunities and generating and implementing new ideas that contribute to radical and incremental innovations. (2) Proactive behavior reflects the entrepreneurial employee's initiative and self-starting nature. (3) Risk is always entailed in intrapreneurship. Because intrapreneurs behave proactively, want to change the status quo, override standard job descriptions, and disregard higher management permission (Rigtering & Weitzel, 2013). Thus, these features imply a range of behaviors and activities employees can participate in. Such as searching for and developing ideas, networking behaviors, identifying opportunities and threats, nurturing ideas, and marketing those to peers and management in the company, make an effort to apply these ideas, and accepting the potential risks (Afsar et al., 2017; De Jong et al., 2015).

3.4.1. Innovative behavior:

Innovation is the most feature used in defining intrapreneurship (Gawke et al., 2019; Neessen et al., 2019). It is a central characteristic of any entrepreneurial activity in organizations (De Jong et al., 2015). Employee engagement in the process of innovation is the core of intrapreneurship (Alam, Kousar, Shabbir, & Kaleem, 2020; Sinha & Srivastava, 2013). An intrapreneur is an employee who introduces and implement innovations (Rigtering & Weitzel, 2013). Moreover, Afriyie et al. (2020) argued that many dimensions of intrapreneurship (new business venturing and strategic renewal) could be dispensed with innovation because the detailed description of them could culminate into innovativeness as it includes various activities; such as identifying new opportunities and ideas in terms of process, product, technology, and markets

Innovative behavior is defined as the employee tendency to engage in creativity and experimentation activities within a work role, group, or organization to introduce new products, services, or processes (De Jong et al., 2015; Moriano et al., 2014; Wakkee, Elfring, & Monaghan, 2010). It is intentional behavior to produce and implement new and

useful ideas (Bos-Nehles, Renkema, & Janssen, 2017). Employees produce and generate ideas independently or search for new ideas in their environment. Then communicate these ideas to colleagues and managers to receive feedback, support, and resources such as time, money, and people to start the implementation process, which begins by preparing implementation plans, predicting potential problems, and developing contingency plans. Then it is important to overcome obstacles, barriers and resistance during the implementation process in order to reach an innovative output (De Jong & Den Hartog, 2010; Lukes & Stephan, 2017).

Innovative behavior is a broader concept that includes employees' creativity (generate ideas) and promotes and implements those ideas. So that, it is expected to reach innovative outputs such as renewing products, services, procedures processes, or new production methods and management systems (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017; Lukes & Stephan, 2017).

3.4.2. Proactive behavior:

Proactive behavior is an essential behavioral aspect of intrapreneurship and is positively related to intrapreneurial intentions and behaviors (Afriyie et al., 2020). As it reflects the self-starting nature of employee intrapreneurship (Gawke et al., 2019; Wakkee et al., 2010). Proactive behavior is defined as employee self-initiated and future-focused action that aims to change and improve the situation or oneself (De Jong et al., 2015; Parker & Collins, 2010). Proactive behavior refers to pioneering and acting according to the expectancy of future needs, changes, or challenges to reach new opportunities before others (Moriano et al., 2014; Wakkee et al., 2010). These definitions reflect three descriptions of proactive behavior; self-starting, change-focused, and future-oriented (Segarra-Ciprés, Escrig-Tena, & García-Juan, 2019).

First, proactive behavior is a self-starting behavior, as it is associated with pioneering behavior and initiatives taken to discover opportunities and attempts to innovate and lead rather than follow (Afriyie et al., 2020; De Jong et al., 2015; Segarra-Ciprés et al., 2019). Second, proactive behavior is a change-focused behavior, as it refers to an action that employees take to increase employees' capacity to modify and adjust their environments and emphasize individual strengths and enhance performance (Segarra-

Ciprés et al., 2019). Proactive behavior aims to improve the organization's internal environment or the fit between the organization and its external environment (De Jong et al., 2015). Third, Proactive behavior is a future-oriented behavior, it representing a forward-looking perspective and long-term vision of the future characterized by high awareness of external trends and events, and anticipating them, preparing to respond to them (De Jong et al., 2015; Valsania, Moriano, & Molero, 2016).

3.4.3. Risk-taking:

Valsania et al. (2016) argued that both innovation and proactiveness are challenging extra-role behaviors to offer ideas and implement changes to improve the organization. This type of behaviors can be argumentative and may involve breaking some rules so that such behaviors carry some potential risk for the individual or the organization. So, Risk-taking is the third defining feature of entrepreneurial behavior.

Risks, in general, indicate that unpredicted or unfortunate events can take place (De Jong et al., 2015). Risk-taking is defined as taking courageous actions by venturing into the unknown and misty circumstances and investing significant resources in new ideas without full knowledge of the results (De Jong et al., 2015; Moriano et al., 2014; Wakkee et al., 2010). It is a preference case for a double face situation that can result in a rewarding outcome if succeeded. On the other hand, it can result in undesirable consequences if failed (Valsania et al., 2016).

In addition to the risks of failure to achieve the desired outcome of employees' entrepreneurial behavior, Intrapreneur may face psychological, social, and/or personal risks, for example, resistance from peers, reputation damage, and may even lose his job (De Jong et al., 2015; Gawke et al., 2019).

4. Innovation climate:

In general, the concept of climate describes the contextual conditions that surround people at a particular time related to their feelings, thoughts, and behavior (Mehmood, Jian, & Waheed, 2019) and shape their expectations about interactions in these conditions (Liu, Chow, Zhang, & Huang, 2019). In organizational settings, climate indicates the work environment characteristics that the employees perceive directly or indirectly and affect their work behavior and attitudes (Ostroff, Kinicki, & Tamkins, 2003; Zuraik & Kelly, 2019).

4.1. Organizational climate and psychological climate:

Naturally, although people may be exposed to the same environmental conditions, there will be actual differences in meanings and perceptions associated with these environmental conditions (James et al., 2008). Because first, individual values differences and their compatibility with the climate. Second, every employee has different cognitive and affective processes, moods, and emotions. Third, differences in how each employee might be treated (Kruft, Gamber, & Kock, 2018). So, scholars differentiate between the individual personal perceptions of the climate, which is called "psychological climate," and the shared perceptions result from aggregates of psychological climate, which is called "organizational climate" (James et al., 2008).

According to the psychological perspective, the climate is the individual description of organizational practices and procedures. Consequently, it is studied at the individual level and not aggregated to the organizational level (Baltes, Zhdanova, & Parker, 2009). Psychological climate describes the day-to-day psychological environment and the emotional atmosphere that significantly affect people's behavior (Minh Ngoc & Cliquet, 2019). Then, a logical extension of psychological climate is when individuals agree on and combine these perceptions to an organizational level (James et al., 2008). Accordingly, organizational climate is defined as the shared meanings, perceptions, and beliefs employees formed about the policies, practices, and procedures through their experience and observations of the behaviors that are rewarded, supported, and expected (Jiang, Wang, & Weng, 2020; Ostroff et al., 2003; Schneider, Ehrhart, & Macey, 2011, 2013). This study

is interested in psychological climate perceptions at the individual level as a starting point in defining innovation climate.

4.2. The concept of innovation climate:

The previous definition of climate, whether psychological or organizational, includes many perceptions about aspects of the environment that may affect the employees. So, researchers adopt more narrowly concepts of climate focus more on specific aspects of work climates such as safety climate, ethics climate, justice climate, customer service climate, creativity and innovation climate, which is the scope of the current study (Amabile et al., 1996; Minh Ngoc & Cliquet, 2019; Newman, Round, Wang, & Mount, 2020).

Appropriately, innovation climate could be defined through organizational climate elements that relate to and support creativity such as top management support, autonomy, resources availability, and collaboration (Ren & Zhang, 2015). Likewise, Krufft et al. (2018) determined seven best and most frequently supported creativity-relevant dimensions of climate, which are: the organizational openness and flexibility toward creative ideas and change, reflexivity on objectives, strategies, and work processes, support and understanding from the immediate supervisor, employees participation in decision-making, employees safety to speak up, communication throughout the organization and the interdepartmental trust and cooperation.

In a like manner, innovation climate could be described as the extent to which an organization encourages its employees to take initiative and investigate creativity ideas to increase the degree of the actual innovation (Übius, Alas, & Elenurm, 2013). Innovation climate is defined as the extent to which the firm encourages and builds a climate that supports creativity (Oke, Prajogo, & Jayaram, 2013b). And the degree to which the norms and values in the organization enhance creativity (Dhar, 2015).

Otherwise, most innovation climate definitions revolve around employees' perceptions about to what extent the climate stimulates creativity and innovation (Newman et al., 2020). Innovation climate refers to employees' perception of the degree to which an organization supports and encourages its staff to take the initiative to explore creative ideas that foster innovation within the organization (Agnihotri et al., 2019; Chan & Liu, 2012; Chan et al., 2014). And it is reflected the employee cognitive experience of the creativity

and innovation environment in the organization (Zhang, Zheng, & Darko, 2018), reflected the employee's perception about to what extent procedures, policies, and behaviors in the organization encourage new idea creation and implementation (Mehmood et al., 2019). In such a climate, employees believe that their organization promotes innovative behavior, tolerates the related risks (Guo & Jin, 2019), and will reward their creative behavior (Kermani & Solhdoost, 2017).

Referring to the aforementioned concept of psychological climate, innovation climate can be viewed as a subjective concept because it reflects the individual personal perception about the environmental factors (such as policies, processes, and managerial behavior) that motivate creativity (Zhou & Zhang, 2017). So, it is vulnerable to change. Additionally, the innovation climate is intangible but real. It is intangible because it is difficult to define and evaluate it in terms of costs and benefits. Real because it significantly affects people's behaviors toward generating ideas, sharing them, and developing them into profitable projects (Minh Ngoc & Cliquet, 2019).

Climate for creativity and innovation is broader than actual innovation since it includes organizational processes, activities, and behaviors that support innovation, which can be considered the final innovation climate goal. Innovation climate concerns employees' perceptions that may or may not achieve actual innovation (Demircioglu & Berman, 2019).

In this research, innovation climate reflects employees' perceptions about the organization's openness to change, its support for new ideas, and its tolerance of member diversity. In addition, the degree to which resources were perceived as adequate in the organization (Park & Jo, 2018; Scott & Bruce, 1994).

5. Theoretical background and hypotheses:

5.1. Psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors:

Concerning the previous definition of employees' entrepreneurial behaviors, risk-taking is embedded in any entrepreneurial activity. Entrepreneurial behaviors essentially focus on challenging the status quo and changing the customary routines in organizations, which may carry physical, social, and psychological risks for individuals in organizations and may lead them to avoid participating in such risky behaviors (Afriyie et al., 2020; Afsar et al., 2017; De Jong et al., 2015; De Jong & Wennekers, 2008; Gawke et al., 2019).

In the same context, psychological safety reduces interpersonal risks and encourages risk-taking behaviors (Newman et al., 2017; Leung et al., 2015; Agarwal & Farndale, 2017; Edmondson, 1999). Psychological safety describes perceptions of the consequences of taking interpersonal risks in the workplace (Edmondson, 1999b; Edmondson & Lei, 2014) and of acting in a way that may be risky (e.g., proposing a new idea) (Kark & Carmeli, 2009). The more harmless these consequences, the more open the environment to communicate new ideas and the less trepidation concerning failure (Palanski & Vogelgesang, 2011). Therefore, psychological safety help to reinforce risk-taking.

Depending on the previous promise that psychological safety promotes risk-taking, studies investigate the relationship between psychological safety and other risky behaviors (e.g., creativity, innovation, and proactivity) that simultaneously entrepreneurial behaviors. Creativity, for example, introduces novel ideas, challenges the status quo, increases ambiguity and uncertainty, and faces the risk of failure and mistakes (Carmeli et al., 2010; George, 2007), meanwhile, generating creative ideas is the key trigger for innovation and consequently for intrapreneurship (Blanka, 2019; Neessen et al., 2019).

This risky nature of creativity requires the organizational context to have some signals of safety to make employees feel safe to participate in creative activities (George, 2007). Especially, psychological safety which promotes thinking of new ideas, exploring different directions, and behaving creatively (Kark & Carmeli, 2009a), encourages employees to feel free from any potential negative consequences and show their true self. Hence, employees' involvement in creative endeavors is increasing (Carmeli et al., 2010).

Likewise, studies have found that psychological safety plays a significant role in linking other variables to creativity. For example, the relationship between leadership and follower creativity, Carmeli et al. (2010) argue that psychological safety is flourished through relational leadership as a key social-psychological mechanism motivate people to give up caution and share in creativity. Therefore, psychological safety mediates the relationship between leader inclusiveness and employee creativity.

Moreover, depending on social information processing theory, Jiang and Gu (2016) found that abusive supervisors who do not tolerate error and blame employees publicly weaken employees' psychological safety, which leads them to abandon creativity in work. In contrast to a humble leader who admits his limitations, appreciates follower ideas and suggestions, seek feedback and looks at mistakes as normal even that could contribute to learning. Such behaviors carry important information to the follower that he also can speak up and express himself. This feeling of psychological safety encourages employees to show creativity at work (Wang et al., 2018).

Furthermore, Kim, Park, and Kim (2019) found that employee's perception of psychological safety has a positive effect on his individual-level creativity and then spread all over the team-level. Also, they found that psychological safety has a mediating role in the relationship between transformational leadership and team creativity. Furthermore, Yang, Li, Liang, and Zhang (2019) endorse that psychological safety strengthens the indirect mediation effect of thriving at work between paradoxical leader behavior and employee creativity.

From creativity to creativity implementation, Agarwal and Farndale (2017) argued that psychological safety established the psychological conditions required for creativity implementation as it supports risk-taking behavior, overcomes social rejection anxiety and affords psychological and social resources necessary for executing creativity. Moreover, Thorgren and Caiman (2019) discussed the key role of psychological safety in implementing agile methods. When team members feel psychologically safe, they will have the intrepidity to criticism constructively the weaken point to improve it, evaluate their own progress honestly and share information. This, in turn, facilitates the process of communication between different cultures and overcome cultural challenges when applying agile methods.

Considering prior research on innovative behavior specifically, reducing employees' sense of risk is the mechanism behind the relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior, despite the different levels of analysis. At the organizational level, the organizational climate for psychological safety reduces personal threats, censors, ridicule, or penalties for proposing a new idea or unfamiliar approaches. Thus, it promotes innovative outputs at the organizational level, such as process innovations (Baer & Frese, 2003) and product-, process-, service-, and business model innovation capabilities (Andersson et al., 2020).

At the team level, Edmondson, Bohmer, and Pisano (2000) argued that psychological safety encourages innovation by allowing open and direct conversation about the new technology used by the team, which in turn induce creating and emerging new ideas that help in implementing the technology successfully or modifying it for new applications. Burke, Stagl, Salas, Pierce, and Kendall (2006) debated that team psychological safety plays an essential role in many phases of the team adaptation cycle, which finally manifested in team innovation. Because psychological safety enables team members to speak up, suggest, discuss the proposed plan. It also encourages team members to accept mutual performance monitoring, support backup behavior, and increase implicit coordination during plan execution.

Post et al. (2009) stated that team members' sense of psychological safety is considered a key element of team dynamics. Because individuals are not afraid of criticism or rejection from the rest of the team, they will contribute valuable information and opinions, even dissent opinions. Subsequently, it will affect team members' innovative behaviors positively. Furthermore, for the same previous reasons, Post (2012) suggested that teams with more psychological safety can draw on unique knowledge and information held by individual members to produce innovation.

Moreover, Lee et al. (2011) stated that team psychological safety is a crucial element of a project team's intellectual capital, and it will enhance manufacturing process innovation implementation technical performance. Accordingly, Gu, Wang, and Wang (2013a) argue that psychological safety encourages team members to take risks under uncertainty. Thus, they found that it positively affects innovation and mediates the

relationship between the structural, cognitive, and relational capital and innovation in R&D teams where risk-taking is critical.

Furthermore, Zhu, Yao, and Zhang (2019) argue that feeling psychologically safe helps to effectively use the talents of team members, unlike feeling insecure in which members tend to hide ideas as they fear ridicule or personal criticism. Accordingly, they found that psychological safety strengthens the mediated role of psychological empowerment in the relationship between empowering leadership and innovative behavior.

The same mechanisms are supposed to apply at the individual level of the relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior. Because, at any level of analysis, psychological safety converges around a single, unifying principle: the importance of reducing interpersonal risk in the workplace (Edmondson & Lei, 2014; Frazier et al., 2017). Psychological safety, at the individual level, reflects the employee's personal evaluation of his/her willingness to take interpersonal risks in the workplace, not the perceptions about the formal and informal organizational practices and procedures (e.g., Baer & Frese, 2003; Andersson et al., 2020) or the shared belief among team members (e.g., Gu, Wang, & Wang, 2013; Post, 2012; Zhu, Yao, & Zhang, 2019).

Previous studies found that psychological safety promotes employees' innovative behavior at the individual level. Psychological safety reduces the employees' expectations about image risk and motivates them to improve their social image through innovation attempts (Yuan & Woodman, 2010). Also, it reduces the risks of failure related to innovation (Leung et al., 2015). Likewise, Javed, Naqvi, Khan, Arjoon, and Tayyeb (2017) argued that if employees feel safe to take risks in the work setting, they will abandon defensive behaviors and engage in innovative work behavior, especially if the leadership is supportive.

In the context of proactivity, through a higher level of psychological safety, leaders can support followers to take interpersonal risks and do not fear negative outcomes of behaving proactively in the workplace (Chen, Jiang, Zhang, & Chu, 2019).

In conclusion, this study argued that psychological safety reduces perceived risks in the workplace. Therefore, it promotes risky behaviors like creativity, innovation, and proactivity. Accordingly, it has a positive effect on entrepreneurial behavior as all.

H1. Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H1a: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' innovative behavior.

H1b: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' proactive behavior.

H1c: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' risk-taking.

5.2. Psychological safety and error orientations:

Errors are primarily perceived as unfavorable events for individuals as they cause stress, embarrassment, guilt, anger, shame, fear of losing face, and so forth (Zhao & Olivera, 2006; Zhao, 2011; Rausch, Seifried, & Harteis, 2017). Because of errors' negative consequences, employees become more cautious and fearful in dealing with situations that they did not previously know where errors are expected. The more severe these negative consequences are, the more conservative and rigid the employee is in the face of an error situation. On the contrary, if employees feel safe from these negative consequences, they will be more open and flexible toward errors and take the risk to err.

Psychological safety reduces the negative consequences of errors. Psychological safety expresses one's beliefs about how others will respond when he asks questions, seek feedback, report a mistake, or come up with a new idea. According to the expected consequences, individuals decide whether to perform these behaviors or not. For example, if there are negative consequences such as embarrassment in error situations, the employee will view the errors as a threat and won't deal with them openly. But if the consequences do not carry a personal threat, he can communicate about errors, discuss concerns, seek help, and learn (Cannon & Edmondson, 2001; Edmondson et al., 2004; Nembhard & Edmondson, 2006). Consequently, psychological safety support employees to adopt positive attitudes toward errors.

The core idea of error orientation is to use errors as enhancers of learning (Rybowiak et al., 1999). Previous studies found that psychological safety positively affects learning from errors because psychological safety encourages engaging in open and

reflective learning behaviors. Enabling employees to discuss errors and request clarification from colleagues (Roussin, Larraz, Jamieson, & Maestre, 2018). Psychological safety is critical for facilitating failure-based learning behaviors. Because it develops a shared belief that the work unit is a safe environment for interpersonal risk-taking, there are no negative consequences for speaking up, such as embarrassment, rejection or punishment. Thus, psychological safety mediates the relationship between social capital and failure-based learning behaviors (Carmeli, 2007).

Moreover, Carmeli and Gittell (2009) investigate how organizations can support employees to learn from organizational failures? They found that high-quality relationships manifested in shared goals, shared knowledge, and mutual respect enable the development of psychological safety, which in turn facilitates learning from failures. Because learning is a process in which members are engaged in “asking questions, seeking feedback, experimenting, reflecting on results, and discussing errors or unexpected outcomes of actions”, psychological safety is vital. Recently, Ye, Wang, and Li (2019) argued that psychological safety reduces interpersonal risks related to the process of learning from errors. Thus, it promotes employees’ learning from errors. Moreover, they found that psychological safety mediates the positive relationship between inclusive leadership and employees’ learning from errors.

Based on the above arguments, the study suggests two mechanisms of how psychological safety help in forming positive error orientations. First, psychological safety allows high-quality interpersonal relations. This is evidenced by the relationship with learning from errors because psychological safety affects this type of learning by allowing high-quality interpersonal relations that facilitate open discussion and learning (Carmeli, 2007; Carmeli & Gittell, 2009). Learning from errors is a coping strategy after the error occurs (Farnese et al., 2020). The study expects that psychological safety affects error competence, communication, and thinking about errors through the exact mechanism. These three orientations (competence, communication, and thinking) are coping strategies (Farnese et al., 2020).

But error risk-taking is a prior cognitive appraisal of errors that won't be harmful (Farnese et al., 2020). So, the second mechanism is reducing errors' negative consequences. The study argue that psychological safety promotes error risk-taking by reducing errors'

negative consequences. Psychological safety reduces interpersonal risks as individuals are likely to believe they will be given the benefit of the doubt (Edmondson, 2004) and enables employees to deal with errors without fearing a loss of status, power, respect, or confidence and without feeling humiliated or embarrassed (Edmondson et al., 2004; Edmondson & Lei, 2014). With this feeling, individuals would take error risks.

The two previous mechanisms are complementary, not contradictory because psychological safety works in these two ways together (Leung et al., 2015). Thus, this study suggests that psychological safety would positively affect learning from errors, error competence, error risk-taking, error anticipation, error communication, and thinking about errors.

H2. Psychological safety has a significant, positive direct effect on error orientation.

H2a: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error competence.

H2b: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on learning from errors.

H2c: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error risk-taking.

H2d: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error communication.

H2e: Psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on thinking about errors.

5.3. Error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior:

Previous studies highlighted the importance of seeing errors as an opportunity to learn in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is done in a complex environment and an uncertain context (Frese, 2009). Entrepreneurs face situational factors such as high novelty, time pressure and information overload, dealing with new products, services, etc. (Frese, 2009; Petkova, 2009). In such circumstances, it is more likely that errors will occur. Thus, dealing positively with errors and learning from them becomes vital.

Indeed, errors may play an important role in entrepreneurial learning because errors highlight incorrect assumptions and beliefs and start a process of elaborate analysis that leads to the development of new knowledge (Petkova, 2009). Furthermore, Petkova (2009) proposed a model of entrepreneurial learning that draws on the psychological literature on

errors and failure-driven learning; he argued that errors are likely to trigger learning because negative outcomes tend to be more salient to entrepreneurs than positive ones. This happens through error detection and error correction.

Good entrepreneurs learn lessons from their errors to avoid the final failure (Guo & Zhao, 2010). According to Frese (2009), the more active entrepreneurs are, the more errors they make. Besides, they can't prevent all errors beforehand. So, entrepreneurs should consider a strategy of error management as an alternative and a complement to error prevention. Then, they expect that errors can occur and deal with them to minimize negative error consequences. Furthermore, individual learning from errors, being competent to deal with errors, action orientation when confronted with errors were related to entrepreneurial success.

More specifically, Guo and Zhao (2010) studied three dimensions of entrepreneurs' error orientations (error competence orientation, error communication orientation, and error learning orientation) in different cultures (Chinese and German) and different industries (IT and software, catering and hotel). They found that, in terms of cultures, both Chinese and German entrepreneurs are concerned about coping with errors. But the difference is that German entrepreneurs communicate more about error than Chinese entrepreneurs, and Chinese entrepreneurs pay more attention to learning from errors than German entrepreneurs. In terms of industries, they stated that entrepreneurs' error learning and error communication in the IT industry should be much higher than entrepreneurs in other industries.

In Chinese culture, Wei and Hisrich (2016) indicated that error orientation can strengthen entrepreneurial opportunity identification behavior (knowledge acquisition, competitive scanning, proactive searching, innovative behavior, and collective action) and lead to better entrepreneurial decision making.

However, previous studies showed a relationship between error orientations and entrepreneurship (Frese, 2009; W. Guo & Zhao, 2010; Petkova, 2009; Wei & Hisrich, 2016). No previous studies have examined this relationship in an intrapreneurial context within existing organizations. Because intrapreneurship has the same spirit of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial employees face situations similar to those outside the

organizations (Antoncic & Hisrich, 2003). This study investigates the relationship between positive error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

Inside organizations, innovation, as a part of entrepreneurial behavior, is a process fraught with uncertainty where one submits to the unknown, which shows the beliefs differences between people, leading to many mistakes and errors (Jalonen, 2012). However, errors and mistakes can be considered a necessary part of generating growth (Foster, 2010; Jalonen, 2012). It can be said that innovation is a process of trial and error (Ortt & Smits, 2006). Hence, employees with an error-preparation mindset will be more involved in innovation.

Before errors happen, a positive appraisal of errors leads the employee to have the courage to engage in entrepreneurial behavior. In uncertain situations, Arenas, Tabernero, and Briones (2006) indicate that employees with a high-performance goal orientation have a positive view of errors. They believe that errors will inevitably occur if progress is to be made job sphere, so they take higher error risks. Error risk-taking reflects a high achievement-oriented attitude that drives individuals to accept errors to achieve higher goals (Zotzmann, van der Linden, & Wyrwa, 2019). Thus, Error risk-taking increases employees' willingness to adjust to new and to take responsibility despite potentially unfavorable consequences (Rybowiak et al., 1999).

After errors occur, positive coping strategies are essential for employees to lead to entrepreneurial behavior. Error competence reflects employees' efficacy to cope with error in the short term (Schell & Conte, 2008), and it is related to employee initiative (Rybowiak et al., 1999). It is expected that the employee who has error competence can provide quick ideas and solutions to the daily errors that he faces at work. Likewise, efficacy to cope with error in the long term, represented in learning from errors, is expected to increase the employees' ability to provide radical and innovative solutions to problems and prevent their recurrence in the future.

Analytical thinking about errors and communicating thoughts will help employees behave entrepreneurially. Because when organizational groups interact open-mindedly and take error risks, they develop innovative solutions and recover from mistakes (Tjosvold & Yu, 2007). Accordingly, this study asserts that error competence, learning from errors,

error risk-taking, error communication, and thinking about errors will positively affect the entrepreneurial behavior of employees.

H3. Error orientation has a significant, positive direct effect on employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H3a: Error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' innovative behavior.

H3b: Error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' proactive behavior.

H3c: Error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' risk-taking.

5.4. The mediating role of error orientations:

The current study further argues that positive error orientation should mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior. As proposed above, psychological safety should enhance positive orientation toward errors (H2), which is likely to affect employees' entrepreneurial behavior (H3). In addition to the direct relationship (H1), this study suggests that one of the mechanisms that underlie the ability of employees who feel psychologically safe to become involved in entrepreneurial behavior is their positive error orientation.

Previous studies have shown that psychological safety has a positive effect on learning behavior at both the individual and team levels (Edmondson, 1999; Carmeli & Gittell, 2009; Liu et al., 2014; Wong & Author, 2010; Bstieler & Hemmert, 2010; Ortega et al., 2010). Considering that, the entrepreneurial process can be described as an inherently dynamic process of experimentation and learning (Petkova, 2009; Cope, 2005; Harrison & Leitch, 2005). Adding a learning variable like Error orientation which, to the entrepreneur, means a special learning process (Wei & Hisrich, 2016) can expand our understanding of the relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior.

Before errors occur, this study argue that psychological safety eliminates expected errors' negative consequences. It allows employees to overcome the anxiety and fear of error, enabling them to focus on improvement rather than be concerned about how others will react if they commit an error. When employees feel that their interpersonal

relationships will be safe if they make an error, they will take error risks and engage in entrepreneurial behavior.

After errors occur, psychological safety allows high-quality interpersonal relations, which are necessary for communicating errors, thinking about them, correct them in the short and long term. When employees experience an open mindset in dealing with errors allowed by psychological safety, they will keep working on their innovative ideas and take the lead to implement them. Based on the above arguments, this study hypothesizes:

H4: Error orientation mediates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior.

H4a: Error orientations mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' innovative behavior.

H4b: Error orientations mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' proactive behavior.

H4c: Error orientations mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees' risk-taking.

5.5. Innovation climate as a moderator:

To foster creativity and innovation, it is particularly important to create an organizational climate that is non-threatening psychologically, supports risk-taking and motivates the employees to apply initiative (Sönmez & Yıldırım, 2018). Previous studies were illiterate that innovation climate is necessary for innovation (Popa, Soto-Acosta, & Martinez-Conesa, 2017; Zhang et al., 2018; Shanker, Bhanugopan, Van der Heijden, & Farrell, 2017; Sönmez & Yıldırım, 2018; Zuraik & Kelly, 2019; kruft et al., 2018; Liu, Chow, Zhang, & Huang, 2019).

Building on the relationship between innovation climate and innovative behavior, previous studies investigate the moderation role of innovation climate in enhancing innovation. For example, Zhang & Zhou (2012) argued that the environmental factors moderate the relationship of individuals' thoughts and behaviors; the more positive the environmental factors, the higher the possibility for the individuals to achieve positive outcomes. Significantly, they stated that innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological capital and employee creativity. Oke et al. (2013) found that

innovation climate positively moderated the relationship between supply chain partner innovativeness and product innovation strategy. At the work-unit level, García-Buades et al. (2016) argued that climate for creativity and innovation is a significant moderator in the relationship between team engagement and service performance. Because in a climate for creativity, employees are willing and empowered to direct the team's effort towards achieving good quality and satisfying service. Zhou, Zhang, & Alexandru (2017) also indicate that the innovation climate positively moderates the relationship between customer psychological empowerment and employee service innovation behavior.

Moving this argument from innovation to entrepreneurship, Van Dam et al. (2010) stated that individual competencies might not suffice to achieve corporate entrepreneurship. But the existed moderating conditions might affect this relationship. Therefore, they proposed that a supportive climate will contribute to corporate entrepreneurship by strengthening the effects of individual competencies. Furthermore, Ahmed (2016) found a significant relationship between innovation climate and corporate entrepreneurship.

Climate is a moderating power as it influences the psychological processes of learning (Ekvall & Ekvall, 1996; Kermani & Solhdoost, 2017). When the employee feels that the organization supports creative ideas, accepts the personal differences among employees, and allocates resources to support the proposed innovations, this facilitates the formation of positive errors orientation and translates this into entrepreneurial behavior. Therefore, this study hypothesizes:

H5: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior.

H5a: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' innovative behavior.

H5b: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' proactive behavior.

H5c: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees' risk-taking.

H6: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between Error orientation and entrepreneurial behavior.

H6a: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' innovative behavior.

H6b: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' proactive behavior.

H6c: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' risk-taking.

Our model extends existing research studies by examining innovation climate as a moderator to the mediated relationships between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior via error orientation. This study hypothesizes that the indirect relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior via error orientation depends on the extent to which individuals perceive organizational support for creativity and innovation. Individual who receives high innovation climate are much more likely to feel psychological safety, develop positive attitudes toward errors and behave entrepreneurially.

So, considering the relationships hypothesized in H5 and H6, it is logical to argue that the mediating effect of error orientation between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior is conditional on the moderating effects of innovation climate. Accordingly, this study hypothesizes the following relationship:

H7: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior via error orientation such that the relationship will be stronger and more positive for people with higher innovation climate perceptions.

H7a: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior via error orientations.

H7b: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and proactive behavior via error orientations.

H7c: Innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and risk taking via error orientations.

Figure (2-2): Hypothesized Research Model.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHOD

- 1. Population and sampling (participants)**
- 2. Instruments**
 - 2.1. Measurement
 - 2.2. Translation of instrument
- 3. Questionnaire pilot testing**
 - 3.1. Validity
 - 3.1.1. Content validity
 - 3.1.2. Face validity
 - 3.2. Reliability
- 4. Ethical considerations**
- 5. Data collection procedure**
- 6. Common method variance**
- 7. Data analysis methods**

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, a post-positivist research philosophy is adopted. Considered that, the concepts of the study exist in reality and can be measured objectively and investigate the causal relationships. Though, results can never be certain since humans are inherently biased in their perception of reality. It is only possible to evaluate whether claims are more or less plausible and test rival hypotheses (Schlegel, 2015). Accordingly, this study used a nonexperimental cross-sectional quantitative methodology. A quantitative approach is aligned with the study's interest in building on existing quantitative research in addition to its focus on statistical relationships between study variables.

In light of this, this chapter discusses the methodological choices of the study. It starts with population and sampling, instruments and procedures employed to collect the data. Then, confirmatory factor analysis to assess the reliability and validity of the scales. It ends with data analysis methods used in hypothesis testing.

1. Population and sampling (Participants):

The sample frame for this study consisted of all full-time employees of the information and communication technology companies in smart village, Egypt, which are 8664 employees distributed over 34 companies. According to Saunders et al. (2016), at a 95% confidence level and an error margin of 5%, the sample should be 384 employees. This study utilized a simple random sample in proportion to the size of each company. Data were obtained using a self-report questionnaire collected via human resources management in the companies. Three hundred seventy-nine (379) valid responses were collected. Table (3-1) shows the study population and sample size.

2. Instruments:

Data for this study were collected using a self-administered questionnaire translated from English into Arabic. Preexisting Measurement with established validity and reliability were used to measure the study variables. All of the constructs are measured with a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (5).

**Table (3-1):
Population and sample size.**

Company	Total employees' number	Required sample	Actual responses
Vodafone International Services	2500	110	98
Etisalat	2774	122	125
Valeo	1000	44	20
Advanced Computer Technology (ACT)	520	23	17
Alcatel lucent Egypt -Nokia	549	24	23
Ericsson Egypt Ltd.	801	35	32
SMART Cards Application Company	130	5	6
AION Innovations	6	2	2
Alfagr Advanced Systems	4	2	2
Amwal	3	2	2
ARPPU	3	2	2
Dileny Technologies and Consultations	5	2	2
Eastern Networks Egypt	82	4	4
efinance	70	4	3
El-Amin Computer Center	18	2	2
Expert Investment	6	2	3
Handaz	7	2	2
Huawei Technologies	3	2	2
Intelligent Systems I-SYS	26	2	2
itobpo+e	4	2	2
Khwarizm Consulting	15	2	2
Lifeforce LLC	7	2	2
Master Micro	4	2	2
MNZ Technology Solutions	15	2	2
National System LLC.	21	2	2
Nile Ventures	6	2	2
Promolinks International	10	2	2
Ta2heal	5	2	2
tamkeen4st	9	2	2
Tec Plus	10	2	2
Vidmy	7	2	2
Waste Marche	4	2	2
WideBot	18	2	2
WOREX Technology	22	2	2
	8664	421	379

Note: the required responses at least 2 from each company.

2.1. Measurement:

- 2.1.1. Psychological safety:** Employees' perception of psychological safety was measured using a 7-item scale developed by Edmondson (1999). This scale assesses the extent to which employees felt psychologically safe to take interpersonal risks in the workplace.
- 2.1.2. Error orientation:** According to the aim and scope of the study, only positive facets of orientations toward errors were of interest. Those positive error orientations were adapted from Rybowskiak et al.'s (1999) scale, which is perfectly matches and covers the focus of our study by emphasizing dealing with errors as a self-instructive and self-organized effort that includes not only the conscious analysis of and reflection on the root causes of errors but also the active implementation of changes to prevent or reduce the probability of future errors. This scale consists of four items to capture error competence, four items capture learning from errors, four items capture error risk-taking, four items capture error communication, and five items capture thinking about errors.
- 2.1.3. Employees' entrepreneurial behavior:** entrepreneurial behavior is operationalized using three dimensions; **innovative behavior** was measured using Six items adapted from de Jong & den Hartog (2010), **proactive behavior** was measured using four items adapted from Parker and Collins (2010) and Morrison and Phelps (1999). **Risk-taking** was measured using three items adapted from Zhao et al. (2005) and De Jong et al. (2015).
- 2.1.4. Innovation climate:** psychological innovation climate perceptions at the individual level were assessed using six items adapted from Park & Jo (2018) and Scott and Bruce (1994); three items capture how much individuals viewed the organization as Support for innovation, and three items capture the degree to which resources were perceived as adequate in the organization.
- 2.1.5. Demographics:** The last part of the instrument referred to demographic variables such as gender, age, educational level, career experience and experience in the current job.

2.2. Translation of instrument:

All measures were administered in Arabic. Measures were translated from English to Arabic using the forward-backwards translation method (Behling & Law, 2000). The source questionnaire written in a different language was translated into the targeted questionnaire, which is Arabic. Then the targeted questionnaire was translated again into the source questionnaire. Finally, the researcher compared the two original questionnaires to reach a final and more suitable one.

3. Questionnaire pilot testing:

After translating the questionnaire into Arabic, it is necessary to perform a questionnaire pilot test before collecting the final data (Saunders et al., 2009). The pilot test is needed to ensure that the questionnaire will work properly in the real work setting and be fully understood by sample units. So that, the questionnaire is first administered to a sample of respondents who will be required to respond to it in the final data collection stage. Then, the researcher uses the feedback to ensure that all the respondents understand the questionnaire items in the same way and will respond to them easily. Moreover, Postlethwaite (2005) constituted that the main purpose of pilot testing is to verify whether the questionnaire is properly designed to obtain the needed information from the respondents. More importantly, Saunders et al. (2009) argued that the pilot test might lead to refining questions to help the respondents clearly understand them. They also highlighted that the pilot test helps the researcher evaluate the questionnaire's validity and reliability.

3.1. Validity:

3.1.1. Content validity:

To verify that questionnaire's items really reflect the variables of the construct intended to be measured. An expert panel consisting of six experts* in the field of the study assessed the content validity of the questionnaires. Each questionnaires item was carefully

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Prof. Mohamed Galal Soliman, professor of Business Administration, Mansoura University.
Prof. Mohamed Ghamry Elshawadfy, prof. of Business Administration, Zagazig University.
Prof. Mona Mohamed Sayed Ibrahim, prof. of Business Administration, Mansoura University.
Prof. Mostafa Al kerdawy, prof. of Business Administration, Damietta University.

reviewed to assure alignment and intention to relevant construct and cultural appropriateness. The experts were asked to examine each question through two criteria; “belongness”, is this item essential in measuring the aimed construct? And “simplicity”, Is this item clear and easy for the respondents to understand? Finally, based on the results of the content validity, it was necessary to modify some items to make them more clear, understandable to the potential respondents, appropriate culturally.

3.1.2. Face validity:

After evaluating the content validity of the questionnaire and making the necessary corrections, the face validity of the questionnaire is accessed by five human resources managers in ICT companies in smart village, Egypt. In addition, ten employees of the target population were selected by convenience sampling. After reading and completing the questionnaire, they were asked to comment on the questions' simplicity, meaning, or any ambiguity in the questions, phrases, or words. The corrections are made in case of necessity as the necessary questions are received.

3.2. Reliability:

As a part of the questionnaire pilot testing process, the researcher directed the questionnaire to a convenience sample of 50 employees of the target population. The responses were utilized to assess the initial reliability of the questionnaire before collecting the final data. One of the most common reliability measures is the Cronbach alpha, where the questionnaire is said to be reliable if the value of Cronbach's alpha is greater than or equals 0.7 (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2014). Table (3-2) shows that the value of Cronbach's alpha for the measurement variables is accepted.

4. Ethical considerations:

After questionnaire pilot testing, permission to conduct the study was obtained at the Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics, Egypt, which found that all procedures and ethical considerations were taken in the research.

**Table (3-2):
Cronbach's alpha of questionnaire pilot testing.**

Construct	Numbers of items	Cronbach's alpha
Psychological safety	7	.966
Error competence	4	.946
Learning from errors	4	.962
Error risk taking	4	.967
Error communication	5	.933
Thinking about errors	4	.980
Innovative behavior	6	.938
Proactive behavior	4	.900
Work related risk taking	3	.929
Innovation climate	6	.773

5. Data collection procedure:

Participants were selected randomly by human resources departments were presented with an overview of the study. Participants were also presented with a consent form specifying that their personal information would be anonymous, their responses would be confidential, and voluntary participation. If they agreed to participate, they were asked to complete all questionnaire sections in one sitting. To ensure data quality, only participants who completed 100% of all measures (each in totality, with no items missing) were included in the data analysis process.

After completing the survey, participants were thanked for their participation. Participants were given the researcher's contact information if they wanted more information regarding the study or needed to discuss further their experience participating in the study.

6. Common Method Variance:

Research involving cross-sectional correlational data, such as collected in this study, is vulnerable to common method variance. Common Method Variance (CMV) refers to the systematic error variance shared among the variables due to the measurement technique rather than the measured, theoretical constructs (Tehseen, Ramayah, & Sajilan, 2017). Essentially occurs in survey research when all data are collected using the same

method (in this case, self-reported questionnaire), possibly resulting in the spurious inflating or deflating of relationships (Jordan & Troth, 2020).

To limit the potential impact of CMV before collecting the final data, First, participants were informed in the orientation of each scale that there were no right or wrong answers to reduce the willingness of participants to present socially desirable responses. Secondly, participants were informed that anonymity was protected to minimize the evaluation apprehension. Thirdly, participants were oriented to recall a specific context related to the scale, for example, thinking about the errors that already happened while responding to the error orientation scale (Tehseen et al., 2017).

7. Data analysis methods:

This study used a moderated-mediation analysis approach, also known as conditional indirect effect analysis, defined as the magnitude of an indirect effect at a particular value of a moderator (Hayes, 2013; Preacher, Rucker, & Hayes, 2007). In other words, this study aimed to determine if the mediating role of error orientations between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior depends on innovation climate's values (moderation).

With these considerations, the present study involved path analysis employing a Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) macro named PROCESS (Hayes, 2017). PROCESS was selected as an advanced regression-based approach developed for assessing complex mediation, moderated mediation models, and the conditional indirect effect.

PROCESS uses ordinary least squares (OLS) regression to estimate the parameters of each of the equations in the model independently, instead of maximum likelihood estimates (MLE) used by SEM to solve the entire system of equations simultaneously through iteration. Nevertheless, it focuses on the indirect effect and statistics in conditional process analysis that integrates the pieces to contemplate the model as a whole rather than just its pieces (Hayes, Montoya, & Rockwood, 2017).

Despite this difference between PROCESS and SEM, it still provides similar or identical results. Furthermore, PROCESS offers bootstrapping capabilities, utilizes conditional process modeling, allows estimating model coefficients, standard errors, t and

p values, easy to use and free. Thus, it has become a popular method across disciplines (Hayes, 2017; Hayes et al., 2017; Hayes & Rockwood, 2020).

Testing the hypothesis in this study is conducted in three steps:

Step 1: Test the direct relationships: A linear regression was conducted using SPSS to test direct relationships hypotheses (1, 2, and 3). To determine if this hypothesis is supported, alpha levels were set at .05 (p must be $< .05$).

Step 2: Test the mediation: Hypothesis 4 was tested using SPSS macro PROCESS Model 4 (Hayes, 2013) and 1,000 bootstraps resamples. Support for this hypothesis was determined if the confidence interval (bootstrap value) did not include “0.”

Step 3: Test the moderation and conditional indirect effect: hypothesis 5, 6 and 7 were tested using SPSS macro PROCESS Model 17 (Hayes, 2013) and 1,000 bootstraps resamples. Support for those hypotheses was determined if the confidence interval (bootstrap value) did not include “0.”

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

- 1. Sample characteristics**
- 2. Descriptive statistics**
- 3. Confirmatory factor analysis and measurement model**
 - 3.1. Measurement model
 - 3.2. Reliability assessment
 - 3.3. Validity assessment
 - 3.4. Common Method Variance (CMV) assessment
- 4. Hypothesis testing**
 - 4.1. Step 1: Test of direct relationships
 - 4.2. Step 2: Test of mediation
 - 4.3. Step 3: Test of moderation and conditional indirect effect

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

This chapter outlines the data analysis conducted to test the hypothesis. In the beginning, this chapter presents sample characteristics and descriptive statistics. Then, it displays the hypothesis test results step by step until it concludes with the entire hypothesized model.

1. Sample characteristics:

Three hundred seventy-nine participants were recruited for this study, 55.1 percent were males, and 44.9 percent were females. Most participants are youth, as more than 75 percent were under 35 years old. Regarding the educational level, 86.5 percent were university graduates, 11.9 percent had a master's degree, and 1.6 percent had a Ph.D. Sixty-one percent of respondents had a working experience of more than five years, while 60.9 percent spent less than five years in the same position. For detailed demographic information, see table (4-1).

2. Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive statistics for the study variables of interest were calculated. Table (4-2) shows the mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis for the study variables. Mean values for all variables indicate a moderate level except innovation climate, which indicates that participants were generally perceived organizational climate to be less supportive to innovation (scale maximum of 5). Skewness and kurtosis were reported as indicators for normality. Both skewness and kurtosis indicated no problem with normality as $|\text{skewness}| \leq 3.0$ and $|\text{kurtosis}| \leq 10.0$ (Kline, 2015).

3. Confirmatory factor analysis and measurement model:

This study carried out a series of confirmatory factor analyses to examine the distinctiveness of the study constructs and to assess the reliability and validity of the scales used in this research:

**Table (4-1):
Demographic variables: sample characteristics (n = 379)**

Variable	n	%
Gender:		
Male	209	55.1
Female	170	44.9
Age:		
Less than 25	93	24.5
From 25 to Less than 30	90	23.7
From 30 to less than 35	107	28.0
From 35 to less than 40	49	13.2
From 40 to less than 45	18	4.7
More than 45	22	5.8
Education:		
University level	328	86.5
Master	45	11.9
PhD	6	1.6
Career Experience:		
Less than 5 years	147	38.8
From 5 to less than 10	115	30.3
From 10 to less than 15	77	20.3
From 15 to less than 20	23	6.1
More than 20	17	4.5
Job Experience:		
Less than 5 years	231	60.9
From 5 to less than 10	118	31.1
From 10 to less than 15	19	5.0
From 15 to less than 20	10	2.6
More than 20	1	.3

Table (4-2):
Descriptive statistics for variable measures

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Skewness	Kurtosis
Psychological safety	2.8590	1.05084	-.086	-1.345
Error competence	2.9571	.90491	-.086	-.928
Learning from errors	3.6153	.96581	-.757	-.133
Error risk taking	2.9429	1.12646	.177	-1.042
Error communication	2.7030	1.03507	-.134	-1.308
Thinking about errors	3.4637	1.00483	-.483	-.593
Innovative behavior	2.9378	.85500	-.101	-.836
Proactive behavior	2.8080	.87851	.235	-.590
Work related risk taking	2.9288	1.13729	.013	-1.048
Innovation climate	1.4824	.52631	-.085	-1.177

3.1. Measurement Model:

To test our proposed model, the researcher first examined and compared two measurement models; Model one was the ten-factor model representing all latent variables as a first order. The second model was an eight-factor model combining innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and risk-taking into one factor, “employees' entrepreneurial behavior”, as a second-order factor. Moreover, each model was assessed with six fit indices: GFI, the goodness of fit index, AGFI, adjusted goodness of fit indices, CFI, comparative fit index, TLI, Tucker–Lewis index, RMSEA, root mean square error of approximation, SRMR, standardized root mean square residual.

Table (4-3):
Results of confirmatory factor analysis of the measurement models

Measurement models	χ^2	df	χ^2/df	GFI	SRMR	AGFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA
			1 >-< 3	>0.90	<0.08	>0.90	>.90	>0.90	<0.06
Ten factor model	2141.679	981	2.183	.806	0.050	.777	.933	0.939	0.056
Eight factor model	2376.225	1001	2.374	.778	0.058	.750	.881	0.927	0.060

As shown in Table (4-3), although there was no big difference between the two models, the eight-factor model had some validity concerns. Regarding discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE for entrepreneurial behavior is less than its correlation with psychological safety and error communication. As well, the composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) for entrepreneurial behavior were less than 0.70 and 0.50, respectively. So, the researcher depended on the Ten-factor model as it fits our data, suggesting that our respondents could distinguish the focal constructs clearly.

The hypothesized ten-factor model demonstrates an acceptable fit to the data ($\chi^2 = 2141.679$, $df = 981$, $\chi^2/df = 2.183$, $CFI = .806$, $TLI = .933$, $RMSEA = 0.056$, $SRMR = 0.050$) (Hair et al., 2014; Thakkar, 2020). Then, the reliability and validity of the scales were assessed.

3.2. Reliability assessment:

Indicator reliability: The individual reliability of each item is given by the loading or correlation between the item and the construct. As a rule of thumb, all factor loadings should be statistically significant, and standardized loading estimates should be 0.5 or higher, and ideally 0.7 or higher (Hair et al., 2014). As shown in Table (4-4), all factor loadings exceed 0.7 except PS4, Pro2, and RS1, which are still accepted as it exceeds 0.5.

Internal consistency reliability: In addition to Cronbach's alpha which remains a commonly applied estimate, although it may understate reliability, the composite reliability (CR) coefficient was calculated because it is more adequate than Cronbach's alpha, as it does not depend on the attributes associated with each concept. For either reliability, an estimate is that .7 or higher suggests good reliability (Hair et al., 2014). Cronbach's alpha (α) and composite reliability (CR) values were above the suggested minimum value of 0.70 for all constructs.

**Table (4-4):
Individual loadings, Cronbach's alpha, CR and AVE.**

Construct	Indicators	Individual loadings	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE	
Psychological Safety (PS)	PS1	0.944	.959	0.962	0.786	
	PS2	0.939				
	PS3	0.931				
	PS4	0.577				
	PS5	0.934				
	PS6	0.939				
	PS7	0.882				
Error Orientations	Error competence (EC)	EC1	0.852	.911	0.904	0.702
		EC2	0.851			
		EC3	0.845			
		EC4	0.801			
	Learning from errors (LearnE)	LE1	.929	.937	0.940	0.797
		LE2	.794			
		LE3	.939			
		LE4	.903			
	Error risk taking (ERT)	ERT1	.861	.947	0.947	0.817
		ERT2	.909			
		ERT3	.933			
		ERT4	.911			
	Error communication (ECom)	ECom1	.920	.948	0.949	0.788
		ECom2	0.927			
		ECom3	0.869			
		ECom4	0.883			
ECom5		0.835				
Thinking about errors (ThinkE)	TE1	0.885	.951	0.951	0.830	
	TE2	0.938				
	TE3	0.911				
	TE4	0.909				
Intrapreneurship	Innovative behavior (INNO)	Inn1	0.874	.940	0.941	0.728
		Inn2	0.901			
		Inn3	0.788			
		Inn4	0.867			
		Inn5	0.809			
		Inn6	0.874			
	Proactive behavior (PRO)	Pro1	0.903	.802	0.866	0.626
		Pro2	0.524			
		Pro3	0.794			
		Pro4	0.883			
Work related Risk taking (Risk)	Risk1	0.91	.928	0.929	0.815	
	Risk2	0.893				
	Risk3	0.905				
Innovation climate	Support for innovation (SI) (0.973)	SI1	0.856	.877	0.847	0.739
		SI2	0.936			
		SI3	0.853			
	Resource supply (RS) (0.729)	RS4	0.664			
		RS5	0.810			
		RS6	0.718			

3.3. Validity assessment:

Convergent validity: Convergent validity represents the common variance between the indicators and their construct, and it is measured by the average variance extracted (AVE). The higher the AVE value, the more representative the construct indicators on which they load are. An AVE of 0.5 or higher suggests adequate convergence. All AVEs for all study constructs exceed 0.5, suggesting adequate convergence.

Discriminant validity: The AVE square root should be higher than the correlation shared between the construct and other constructs to assess discriminant validity among constructs. As shown in Table (4-5), the square root of AVE is higher than the correlation shared between the construct and other constructs (Hair et al., 2014).

**Table (4-5):
Correlations and square roots of AVEs.**

	PS	EC	LearnE	ERT	Ecom	Think	INNO	PRO	Risk	Climate
PS	(0.887)									
EC	0.570***	(0.838)								
LearnE	0.586***	0.495***	(0.893)							
ERT	0.671***	0.589***	0.480***	(0.904)						
Ecom	0.865***	0.463***	0.507***	0.540***	(0.888)					
Think	0.611***	0.656***	0.719***	0.472***	0.570***	(0.911)				
INNO	0.434***	0.323***	0.336***	0.425***	0.409***	0.250***	(0.853)			
PRO	0.332***	0.215***	0.211***	0.371***	0.367***	0.237***	0.489***	(0.791)		
Risk	0.545***	0.384***	0.292***	0.546***	0.466***	0.368***	0.257***	0.322***	(0.903)	
Climate	0.849***	0.461***	0.467***	0.547***	0.840***	0.491***	0.435***	0.362***	0.468***	(0.860)

Notes: (square root of AVE); *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

3.4. Common Method Variance (CMV) assessment:

Statistically, Harman's single-factor test was utilized to investigate potential CMV among the study variables (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, & Podsakoff, 2003). The basic assumption of Harman's single-factor test is that if a substantial amount of CMV is present, one general factor will account for the majority (more than 50 percent) of the covariance among the variables. This test showed that multiple factors were extracted. The first factor

accounted for only 39.8 percent of the total variance, suggesting that common method bias is not likely to be a serious problem with our data.

4. Hypothesis testing:

The hypothesis testing went through three steps to show the effect of the added variables until reaching the final model, as follows:

4.1. Step 1: Test of direct relationships:

In this step, the first three hypotheses about the direct relationship between psychological safety (independent), employees' entrepreneurial behavior (dependent), and error orientations (mediators). To this end, a linear regression analysis was conducted.

Hypothesis 1. stated that psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' entrepreneurial behavior. Employees who feel psychological safety are more likely to show entrepreneurial behavior represented by innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and work-related risk-taking. A simple linear regression was carried out to determine the relationship between psychological safety (as the only predictor) and each entrepreneurial behavior. Table (4-3) illustrates the results of testing hypothesis 1.

**Table (4-6):
Regression analysis: psychological safety and entrepreneurial behaviors.**

Outcome	β	SE	95% CI		t	p	R ²	F	p
			Lower	Upper					
Innovative behavior	.366	.037	.284	.438	9.774	.000	.202	95.523	.000
Proactive behavior	.291	.040	.197	.375	7.197	.000	.121	51.791	.000
Work related Risk taking	.609	.046	.515	.701	13.213	.000	.317	174.582	.000

Hypothesis 1a: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' innovative behavior.

Results indicated that psychological safety significantly affect employee innovative behavior, $\beta = .366$, $t = 9.774$, $p < .001$. Psychological safety positively and significantly explained a portion of the variance in employee innovative behavior, $R^2 = .202$, $F = 95.523$, $p < .001$. Thus, 20% of the variance in employees' innovative behavior was predicted by psychological safety, indicating a large effect size.

Hypothesis 1b: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' proactive behavior.

Likewise, results showed that psychological safety has a significant positive effect on employees' proactive behavior, $\beta = .291$, $t = 7.197$, $p < .001$. Psychological safety positively and significantly explained a portion of the variance in employee proactive behavior, $R^2 = .121$, $F = 51.791$, $p < .001$. Thus, 12% of the variance in employees' proactive behavior was predicted by psychological safety.

Hypothesis 1c: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' risk-taking.

As well, the data showed that psychological safety significantly affects employee risk-taking, $\beta = .609$, $t = 13.213$, $p < .001$. Psychological safety positively and significantly explained a portion of the variance in employee proactive behavior, $R^2 = .317$, $F = 174.582$, $p < .001$. Thus, 31% of the variance in employee risk-taking behavior was predicted by psychological safety.

Therefore, hypothesis 1 was totally supported, emphasizing that psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on employees' innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and risk-taking.

Hypothesis 2. stated that psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error orientation, such that psychological safety would make employees have error competence, learn from errors, take error risks, communicate their errors, and think about errors. A simple linear regression was carried out to determine the relationship between psychological safety and each error orientation.

Hypothesis 2a: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error competence.

As shown in table (4-7), results indicated that psychological safety significantly and positively affect error competence, $\beta = .502$, $t = 13.942$, $p < .000$. Psychological safety positively and significantly explained a portion of the variance in employee error

competence, $R^2 = .340$, $F = 194.389$, $p < .000$. Thus, 34% of the variance in employees' error competence was predicted by psychological safety, indicating a large effect size.

Table (4-7):

Regression analysis: psychological safety and error orientation.

Outcome	β	SE	95% CI		t	p	R^2	F	p
			Lower	Upper					
Error competence	.502	.036	.430	.579	13.942	.000	.340	194.389	.000
Learning from errors	.559	.038	.475	.641	14.885	.000	.370	221.556	.000
Error risk taking	.730	.040	.649	.805	18.077	.000	.464	326.781	.000
Error communication	.877	.023	.830	.922	37.948	.000	.792	1440.029	.000
Thinking about errors	.604	.038	.528	.683	15.839	.000	.400	250.877	.000

Hypothesis 2b: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on learning from errors.

Results indicated that psychological safety significantly and positively affect learning from errors, $\beta = .559$, $t = 14.885$, $p < .000$. Psychological safety positively and significantly explained a portion of the variance in employees' learning from errors, $R^2 = .370$, $F = 221.556$, $p < .000$. Thus, 37% of the variance in employees' learning from errors was predicted by psychological safety, see table (4-7).

Hypothesis 2c: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error risk-taking.

Results indicated that psychological safety significantly and positively affect error risk-taking, $\beta = .730$, $t = 18.077$, $p < .000$. Psychological safety positively and significantly explained a portion of the variance in employees' error risk-taking, $R^2 = .464$, $F = 326.781$, $p < .000$. Thus, psychological safety predicted 46% of the variance in error risk-taking (see table (4-7)).

Hypothesis 2d: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on error communication.

Results indicated that psychological safety significantly and positively affect error communication, $\beta = .877$, $t = 37.948$, $p < .000$. Psychological safety positively and

significantly explained a portion of the variance in communicating about errors, $R^2 = .792$, $F = 1440.029$, $p < .000$. Thus, 79% of the variance in error risk-taking errors was predicted by psychological safety, indicating a large effect size (see table (4-7)).

Hypothesis 2e: psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on thinking about errors.

Results indicated that psychological safety significantly and positively affect thinking about errors, $\beta = .877$, $t = 37.948$, $p < .000$. Psychological safety positively and significantly explained a portion of the variance in employees' thinking about errors, $R^2 = .400$, $F = 250.877$, $p < .000$. Thus, 40% of the variance in thinking about errors was predicted by psychological safety, see table (4-7).

Therefore, support was found for hypothesis 2, emphasizing that psychological safety has a significant positive direct effect on all error orientations; error competence, learning from errors, error risk-taking, error communication, and thinking about errors.

Hypothesis 3. stated that error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' entrepreneurial behavior. When employees have positive attitudes towards error, meaning they have error competence, learn from errors, take error risks, communicate their errors, and think about errors, they behave innovatively, proactively, and take risks in work. A multiple linear regression (Entre method) was employed to determine the relationship between error orientations and each entrepreneurial behavior.

Hypothesis 3a: error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' innovative behavior.

Results indicated that error competence ($\beta = .132$, $t = 2.073$, $p < .05$), learning from errors ($\beta = .204$, $t = 3.345$, $p < .01$), error risk taking ($\beta = .172$, $t = 3.631$, $p < .001$) and error communication ($\beta = .230$, $t = 4.673$, $p < .001$) have a significant positive direct effect on employee innovative behavior. Unexpectedly, thinking about errors ($\beta = -.240$, $t = -3.471$, $p < .01$) has a significant negative direct effect on employee innovative behavior. Error orientations significantly explained a portion of the variance in employee innovative behavior, $R^2 = .275$, $F = 28.335$, $p < .001$. Thus, 27% of the variance in employee innovative behavior was predicted by error orientations, results showed in table (4-8).

Table (4-8):**Regression Analysis: error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior.**

Predictor	Outcome	β	SE	95% CI		t	p	R ²	F	p
				Lower	Upper					
Error competence	Innovative behavior	.132	.064	-.001	.273	2.073	.039	.275	28.335	.000
Learning from errors		.204	.061	.086	.313	3.345	.001			
Error risk taking		.172	.047	.074	.267	3.631	.000			
Error communication		.230	.049	.127	.331	4.673	.000			
Thinking about errors		-.24	.069	-.373	-.108	-3.47	.001			
Error competence	Proactive behavior	-.08	.069	-.218	.073	-1.15	.247	.202	18.898	.000
Learning from errors		-.05	.066	-.198	.086	-.810	.419			
Error risk taking		.239	.051	.134	.344	4.686	.000			
Error communication		.220	.053	.104	.330	4.149	.000			
Thinking about errors		.041	.075	-.114	.186	.553	.581			
Error competence	Risk taking	-.00	.078	-.151	.144	-.062	.951	.383	46.319	.000
Learning from errors		-.16	.075	-.305	-.02	-2.20	.028			
Error risk taking		.455	.058	.349	.564	7.842	.000			
Error communication		.257	.060	.138	.367	4.246	.000			
Thinking about errors		.154	.085	-.003	.308	1.809	.071			

Hypothesis 3b: error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' proactive behavior.

Regarding the relationship between error orientations and employee proactive behavior, only error risk taking ($\beta = .239$, $t = 4.686$, $p < .001$) and error communication ($\beta = .220$, $t = 4.149$, $p < .001$) have a significant positive direct effect on employee proactive behavior. Error orientations significantly explained 20% of the variance in employee proactive behavior, $R^2 = .202$, $F = 18.898$, $p < .001$. see table (4-8).

Hypothesis 3c: error orientations have a significant positive direct effect on employees' risk-taking.

As for the relationship between error orientations and employee risk taking, only error risk taking ($\beta = .455$, $t = 7.842$, $p < .001$) and error communication ($\beta = .257$, $t = 4.246$, $p < .001$) have a significant positive direct effect on risk taking. Surprisingly, learning from errors ($\beta = -.165$, $t = -2.201$, $p < .05$) has a significant negative direct effect on employee risk taking. Error orientations significantly explained 38% of the variance in employee risk taking, $R^2 = .383$, $F = 46.319$, $p < .001$. results showed in table (4-8). Therefore, Hypothesis 3 was partially supported.

4.2. Step 2: Test of mediation:

After knowing the nature of direct relationships, it is time to build the mediation model. These mediation analyses were conducted using the macro PROCESS on SPSS Model 4 (Hayes, 2013) and 1,000 bootstrap resamples. Support for this hypothesis was determined if the confidence interval (bootstrap value) did not include “0.”

Hypothesis 4. stated that error orientations positively mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employee entrepreneurial behaviors. This hypothesis is divided into three (steps) sub-hypotheses according to entrepreneurial behaviors (dependent variable).

Hypothesis 4a: error orientations positively mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees’ innovative behavior.

As shown in table (4-9), results based on 1,000 bootstrapped resamples revealed a significant positive indirect effect by learning from errors (IE = .1127, 95% IC [.0464 to .1764]), error risk-taking (IE = .1227, 95% IC [.0414 to .2033]) and error communication (IE = .1891, 95% IC [.0208 to .3490]) between psychological safety and employee innovative behavior. No evidence of error competence (IE = .0654, 95% IC [-.0005 to .1341]) as a mediator was found. Unexpectedly, thinking about errors (IE = -.1450, 95% IC [-.2238 to -.0607]) has a significant negative indirect effect between psychological safety and innovative behavior. Moreover, the direct relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior becomes non-significant ($\beta = .0209$, $p = .8238$), indicating a full mediation role of error orientations. Still, hypothesis 4a was partially supported because not all error orientations were significant mediators (error competence), and not all error orientations were positive mediators (thinking about errors).

**Table (4-9): Mediation effects of Error orientations
in the relationship between Psychological Safety and Innovative behavior.**

Independent	<i>Path a</i>	Mediators	<i>Path b</i>	Dependent
Psychological Safety	.5023***	Error competence <i>Path C</i> = .0654, 95% CI (-.0005 to .1341)	.1302*	Innovative behavior
	.5592***	Learning from errors <i>Path C</i> = .1127, 95% CI (.0464 to .1764)	.2015**	
	.7304***	Error risk taking <i>Path C</i> = .1227, 95% CI (.0414 to .2033)	.1680***	
	.8769***	Error communication <i>Path C</i> = .1891, 95% CI (.0208 to .3490)	.2156**	
	.6044***	Thinking about errors <i>Path C</i> = -.1450, 95% CI (-.223 to -.060)	-.239***	

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, *Path a* = direct effect (independent \rightarrow mediators), *Path b* = direct effect (mediators \rightarrow dependent), *Path C* = indirect effect ~ significant when CI not containing the value “0”.

Hypothesis 4b: error orientations positively mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employees’ proactive behavior.

Results based on 1,000 bootstrapped resamples showed a significant positive mediating role of error risk taking (IE = .2027, 95% IC [.1187 to .2920]) and error communication (IE = .3292, 95% IC [.1393 to .5044]) in the relationship between psychological safety and employee proactive behavior. While results showed non-statistically significant mediating role of either error competence (IE = .0227, 95% IC [-.0005 to .1341]), learning from errors (IE = -.0143, 95% IC [-.0906 to .0596]) or thinking about errors (IE = .0227, 95% IC [-.0631 to .1152]), results showed in table (4-10). Therefore, partial support was found for hypothesis 4b.

Hypothesis 4c: error orientations positively mediate the relationship between psychological safety and employee risk-taking.

Results based on 1,000 bootstrapped resamples, displayed in table (4-11), showed a significant positive mediating role of error risk taking (IE = .2859, 95% IC [.1995 to .3818]) in the relationship between psychological safety and employee risk taking. While data failed to support the mediating effect of error competence (IE = -.0207, 95% IC [-.0924 to .0535]), error communication (IE = .0020, 95% IC [-.1679 to .1539]) and thinking

about errors (IE = .0965, 95% IC [.0000 to .1895]). Unlike expected, learning from errors (IE = -.1176, 95% IC [-.2077 to -.0358]) has a significant negative indirect mediating effect between psychological safety and risk taking. Therefore, partial support was found for hypothesis 4c.

Table (4-10): Mediation effects of Error orientations in the relationship between Psychological Safety and Proactive behavior.

Independent	<i>Path a</i>	Mediators	<i>Path b</i>	Dependent
Psychological Safety	.5023***	Error competence <i>Path C</i> = -.0290, 95% CI (-.106 to .0492)	-.0577	Proactive behavior
	.5592***	Learning from errors <i>Path C</i> = -.0143, 95% CI (-.090 to .0596)	-.0255	
	.7304***	Error risk taking <i>Path C</i> = .2027, 95% CI (.1187 to .2920)	.2775***	
	.8769***	Error communication <i>Path C</i> = .3292, 95% CI (.1393 to .5044)	.3754***	
	.6044***	Thinking about errors <i>Path C</i> = .0227, 95% CI (-.063 to .1152)	.0376	

Note: **p* < .05, ***p* < .01, ****p* < .001, *Path a* = direct effect (independent → mediators), *Path b* = direct effect (mediators → dependent), *Path C* = indirect effect ~ significant when CI not containing the value “0”.

Table (4-11): Mediating effects of Error orientations in the relationship between Psychological Safety and Risk taking.

Independent	<i>Path a</i>	Mediators	<i>Path b</i>	Dependent
Psychological Safety	.5023***	Error competence <i>Path C</i> = -.0207, 95% CI (-.092 to .0535)	-.0411	Work related Risk taking
	.5592***	Learning from errors <i>Path C</i> = -.1176, 95% CI (-.207 to -.035)	-.2104**	
	.7304***	Error risk taking <i>Path C</i> = .2859, 95% CI (.1995 to .3818)	.3915***	
	.8769***	Error communication <i>Path C</i> = .0020, 95% CI (-.168 to .1539)	.0023	
	.6044***	Thinking about errors <i>Path C</i> = .0965, 95% CI (.0001 to .1895)	.1596	

Note: **p* < .05, ***p* < .01, ****p* < .001, *Path a* = direct effect (independent → mediators), *Path b* = direct effect (mediators → dependent), *Path C* = indirect effect ~ significant when CI not containing the value “0”.

4.3. Step 3: Test of moderation and conditional indirect effect:

We next tested a moderated mediation model to test the moderation role of innovation climate and to check whether the effects of psychological safety (independent variable) on entrepreneurial behaviors (outcome variables) via error orientations (mediator) depend on the level of innovation climate (moderator). To this end, the researcher followed the procedure described by (Preacher et al., 2007) and utilized the SPSS macro PROCESS Model 15 (Hayes, 2013). The presence of a moderating effect was determined to be statistically significant if confidence intervals (CI) did not capture the value of “0.”

Hypothesis 5. stated that innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees’ entrepreneurial behaviors (represented by innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and work-related risk-taking), such that the relationship is amplified with a stronger innovation climate. This hypothesis has three sub-hypotheses as follows:

Hypothesis 5a: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees’ innovative behavior.

Hypothesis 5b: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees’ proactive behavior.

Hypothesis 5c: Innovation climate moderates the relationship between psychological safety and employees’ risk-taking.

Results, as presented in table (4-12), indicated that innovation climate significantly moderate the relationship between psychological safety and risk taking only ($\beta = .6374$, $t = 2.6532$, $p = .0083$, 95% IC [.1650 to 1.1098]). While no evidence was found for the moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between Psychological Safety and Innovative behavior ($\beta = -.2357$, $t = -1.2202$, $p = .2232$, 95% IC [-.6156 to .1442]) and Proactive behavior ($\beta = .1892$, $t = .8992$, $p = .3691$, 95% IC [-.2246 to .6030]).

Table (4-12): Moderating effects of innovation climate on the relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behaviors

Predictor	Moderator	Outcome	β	SE	t	p	95% CI	
							Lower	Upper
Psychological Safety	Innovation climate	Innovative behavior	-.235	.193	-1.220	.223	-.615	.144
		Proactive behavior	.189	.210	.899	.369	-.224	.603
		Work related Risk taking	.637	.240	2.653	.008	.165	1.109

Furthermore, the significant moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between psychological safety and risk-taking is illustrated in figure (4-1). That is, when employees perceive a low innovation climate, psychological safety has a weaker effect on employee risk-taking, and when employees perceive high innovation climate, psychological safety has a stronger effect on employee risk-taking.

Figure (4-1): Innovation climate as a moderator on the relationship between Psychological Safety and Risk-taking.

Hypothesis 6. stated that innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations (error competence, learning from errors, error risk-taking, error communication, and thinking about errors) and employees’ entrepreneurial behaviors (innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and work-related risk-taking).

Hypothesis 6a: innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees’ innovative behavior.

Regarding the moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between error orientations and innovative behavior, results indicated that innovation climate only significantly moderate the relationship between error risk taking and innovative behavior ($\beta = .4247$, $t = 4.6920$, $p < .0001$, 95% IC [.2467 to .6027]). While the moderating effect of innovation climate on the relationship between error competence ($\beta = -.0670$, $t = -.5512$, $p = .5818$, 95% IC [-.3060 to .1720]), learning from errors ($\beta = .0474$, $t = .3876$, $p = .6986$, 95% IC [-.1932 to .2880]), error communication ($\beta = -.2842$, $t = -1.7395$, $p = .0828$, 95% IC [-.5641 to .2349]), thinking about errors ($\beta = .0152$, $t = .1266$, $p = .8993$, 95% IC [-.2204 to .2507]) and innovative behavior was not significant (see table (4-13)).

Table (4-13): Moderating effects of innovation climate.

Predictor	Moderator	Outcome	β	SE	t	p	95% CI	
							Lower	Upper
Error competence	Innovation climate	Innovative behavior	-.067	.121	-.551	.581	-.306	.172
Learning from errors			.047	.122	.387	.698	-.193	.288
Error risk taking			.424	.090	4.692	.000	.246	.602
Error communication			-.284	.163	-1.739	.082	-.605	.037
Thinking about errors			.015	.119	.126	.899	-.220	.250
Error competence	Innovation climate	Proactive behavior	-.289	.132	-2.185	.029	-.549	-.029
Learning from errors			-.006	.133	-.049	.960	-.268	.255
Error risk taking			.285	.098	2.891	.004	.091	.478
Error communication			-.401	.177	-2.255	.024	-.751	-.051
Thinking about errors			.204	.130	1.569	.117	-.051	.461
Error competence	Innovation climate	Work related Risk taking	.067	.151	.443	.657	-.230	.364
Learning from errors			-.022	.152	-.145	.884	-.321	.277
Error risk taking			-.346	.112	-3.079	.002	-.567	-.125
Error communication			-.164	.203	-.810	.418	-.564	.234
Thinking about errors			.053	.149	.358	.720	-.239	.346

The significant moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between error risk-taking and innovative behavior is illustrated in figure (4-2). The relationship between error risk-taking and innovative behavior becomes stronger when employees perceive high innovation climate.

Figure (4-2): Innovation climate as a moderator on the relationship between Error risk-taking and Innovative behavior.

Hypothesis 6b: innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees’ proactive behavior.

Considering the moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between error orientations and proactive behavior, data provide support for moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between error competence ($\beta = -.2894$, $t = -2.1856$, $p = .0295$, 95% IC [-.5497 to -.0290]), error risk taking ($\beta = .2850$, $t = 2.8911$, $p = .0041$, 95% IC [.0912 to .4789]), error communication ($\beta = -.4013$, $t = -2.2553$, $p = .0247$, 95% IC [-.7512 to -.0514]) and employee’s proactive behavior. No evidence was found for the moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between learning from errors ($\beta = -.0066$, $t = -.0495$, $p = .9605$, 95% IC [-.2687 to .2555]), thinking about errors ($\beta = .2047$, $t = 1.5690$, $p = .1175$, 95% IC [-.0519 to .4613]) and employee’s proactive behavior (see table (4-13)).

The significant moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between error competence and proactive behavior is illustrated in figure (4-3). Unexpectedly, innovation climate has a negative moderating effect on the relationship between error competence and proactive behavior, like all unexpected results will have discussed in the next chapter.

Figure (4-3): Innovation climate as a moderator on the relationship between Error competence and Proactive behavior.

Figure (4-4) illustrates the significant moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between error risk-taking and proactive behavior. When employees perceive a high innovation climate, the relationship between error risk-taking and innovative behavior becomes stronger.

Figure (4-4): Innovation climate as a moderator on the relationship between Error risk-taking and proactive behavior.

Figure (4-5) illustrates the significant moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between error communication and proactive behavior. Employees display high proactive behavior when they simultaneously perceive a high innovation climate and communicate highly about their errors.

Figure (4-5): Innovation climate as a moderator on the relationship between Error communication and Proactive behavior.

Hypothesis 6b: innovation climate moderates the relationship between error orientations and employees' risk-taking.

Regarding the moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between error orientations and risk-taking behavior, results indicated that innovation climate only significantly moderate the relationship between error risk taking and work-related risk taking ($\beta = -.3466$, $t = -3.0790$, $p = .0022$, 95% IC [-.5679 to -.1252]). However, the moderating effect of innovation climate on the relationship between error competence ($\beta = .0670$, $t = .4436$, $p = .6576$, 95% IC [-.2302 to .3643]), learning from errors ($\beta = -.0221$, $t = -.1451$, $p = .8847$, 95% IC [-.3213 to .2771]), error communication ($\beta = -.1646$, $t = -.8104$, $p = .4183$, 95% IC [-.5641 to .2349]), thinking about errors ($\beta = .0534$, $t = .3583$, $p = .7204$, 95% IC [-.2396 to .3463]) and work-related risk taking was not significant (see table (4-13)).

Figure (4-6) clarifies the significant moderation effect of innovation climate on the relationship between error risk-taking and work-related risk-taking. An additional surprising result is that when employees perceive a high innovation climate, the relationship between error risk-taking and innovative behavior becomes weaker.

Figure (4-6): Innovation climate as a moderator on the relationship between Error risk-taking and work-related risk-taking.

Hypothesis 7. stated that innovation climate moderates the mediating effect of psychological safety on employees’ entrepreneurial behaviors (innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and work-related risk-taking) via error orientations (error competence, learning from errors, error risk-taking, error communication, and thinking about errors). PROCESS refers to this statistic as an index of moderated mediation. The significance of the conditional indirect effect was based on the moderated mediation index, which depicts the linear association between the moderator (innovation climate) and the indirect effect. Support for this hypothesis was determined depending on if the confidence interval (bootstrap value) does not include “0”.

Hypothesis 7a: innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior via error orientations.

Regarding the moderating effect of innovation climate on the mediating relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior through error orientations, among the five error orientations, the index of moderated mediation indicates that innovation climate moderates the effect of psychological Safety on employee’s innovative behavior via the mediator error risk-taking only (Index = .3102, 95% IC [.1780 to .4691]) due to the confidence interval do not include “0”, see Table (4-14). While the index of moderated mediation produced a non-significant bootstrapped for the rest of the mediators.

**Table (4-14):
Indices of moderated mediation of psychological safety on creativity behavior**

Mediator PS → INNO	Index	BootSE	95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Error competence	-.0337	.0699	-.1750	.0967
Learning from errors	.0265	.0671	-.0943	.1671
Error risk taking	.3102	.0746	.1780	.4691
Error communication	-.2492	.1725	-.5975	.0788
Thinking about errors	.0092	.0731	-.1333	.1628

Additionally, by looking at the conditional indirect effects of psychological safety on innovative behavior via error risk-taking displayed in the table (4-15), the indirect path was stronger at the high levels of innovation climate (Effect = .2424, 95% CI [.1496 to

.3415]) than at the moderate level of innovation climate (Effect = .0791, 95% CI [.0001 to .1567]) while become non-significant at the low levels of innovation climate (Effect = -.0842, 95% CI [-.2098 to .0384]).

Table (4-15):
Conditional indirect effects of psychological safety on innovative behavior.

Mediator PS → INNO	Moderator Condition	Effect	BootSE	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Error competence	“Low” (-1 SD)	.0830	.0479	-.0048	.1818
	“Moderate” (mean)	.0653	.0324	.0043	.1349
	“High” (+1 SD)	.0475	.0501	-.0489	.1489
Learning from errors	“Low” (-1 SD)	.1588	.0441	.0705	.2401
	“Moderate” (mean)	.1727	.0390	.1031	.2555
	“High” (+1 SD)	.1867	.0599	.0764	.3222
Error risk taking	“Low” (-1 SD)	-.0842	.0620	-.2098	.0384
	“Moderate” (mean)	.0791	.0393	.0001	.1567
	“High” (+1 SD)	.2424	.0483	.1496	.3415
Error communication	“Low” (-1 SD)	.2213	.1381	-.0852	.4734
	“Moderate” (mean)	.0902	.0928	-.1002	.2663
	“High” (+1 SD)	-.0410	.1210	-.2750	.1877
Thinking about errors	“Low” (-1 SD)	-.1387	.0530	-.2441	-.0382
	“Moderate” (mean)	-.1338	.0419	-.2172	-.0515
	“High” (+1 SD)	-.1290	.0604	-.2573	-.0029

Hypothesis 7b: innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and proactive behavior via error orientations.

Regarding the moderating role of innovation climate in the mediating relationship between psychological safety and proactive behavior through error orientations, among the five error orientations, the index of moderated mediation indicates that innovation climate moderates the effect of psychological safety on employee’s proactive behavior via error risk-taking only (Index = .2082, 95% IC [.0460 to .3882]) due to the confidence interval do not include “0”, see Table (4-16). In comparison, the index of moderated mediation produced a non-significant bootstrapped for the rest of the mediators.

Table (4-16):**Indices of moderated mediation of psychological safety on proactive behavior**

Mediator PS → PRO	Index	BootSE	95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Error competence	-.1453	.0764	-.2852	.0056
Learning from errors	-.0037	.0875	-.1889	.1570
Error risk taking	.2082	.0890	.0460	.3882
Error communication	-.3519	.1710	-.6750	-.0134
Thinking about errors	.1237	.0789	-.0385	.2783

Further, as shown in table (4-13), the indirect path from psychological safety to proactive behavior via error risk-taking was non-significant at the low levels of innovation climate (Effect = .0728, 95% CI [-.0718 to .2134]), became significant at the moderate level of innovation climate (Effect = .1823, 95% CI [.0915 to .2763]), and became stronger at the high levels of innovation climate (Effect = .2919, 95% CI [.1828 to .4078]).

Table (4-17):**Conditional indirect effects of psychological safety on proactive behavior**

Mediator PS → PRO	Moderator Condition	Effect	BootSE	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Error competence	“Low” (-1 SD)	.0462	.0559	-.0633	.1550
	“Moderate” (mean)	-.0303	.0368	-.1057	.0416
	“High” (+1 SD)	-.1068	.0531	-.2145	.0059
Learning from errors	“Low” (-1 SD)	.0169	.0549	-.1019	.1130
	“Moderate” (mean)	.0149	.0557	-.1030	.1101
	“High” (+1 SD)	.0130	.0863	-.1745	.1601
Error risk taking	“Low” (-1 SD)	.0728	.0733	-.0718	.2134
	“Moderate” (mean)	.1823	.0460	.0915	.2763
	“High” (+1 SD)	.2919	.0569	.1828	.4078
Error communication	“Low” (-1 SD)	.4452	.1454	.1492	.7090
	“Moderate” (mean)	.2600	.1009	.0590	.4812
	“High” (+1 SD)	.0748	.1240	-.1664	.3104
Thinking about errors	“Low” (-1 SD)	-.0380	.0524	-.1374	.0677
	“Moderate” (mean)	.0272	.0474	-.0646	.1242
	“High” (+1 SD)	.0923	.0722	-.0568	.2379

Hypothesis 7c: innovation climate moderates the mediated relationship between psychological safety and risk-taking via error orientations.

Similarly, Regarding the moderating role of innovation climate in the mediating relationship between psychological safety and risk-taking through error orientations, among the five error orientations, the index of moderated mediation indicates that innovation climate moderates the mediating effect of psychological safety on employee's work-related risk-taking via error risk-taking only (Index = -.2532, 95% IC [-.3935 to -.1186]) due to the confidence interval do not include "0", but surprisingly, this moderating effect was negative, see Table (4-18). While the index of moderated mediation produced a non-significant bootstrapped for the rest of the mediators.

Table (4-18):

Indices of moderated mediation of psychological safety on risk taking.

Mediator PS → Risk	Index	BootSE	95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Error competence	.0337	.0738	-.1251	.1696
Learning from errors	-.0123	.0878	-.1754	.1727
Error risk taking	-.2532	.0719	-.3935	-.1186
Error communication	-.1444	.1842	-.5278	.2098
Thinking about errors	.0323	.0858	-.1350	.2058

Therefore, as shown in table (4-15), the indirect path from psychological safety to risk-taking via error risk-taking was weaker at the high levels of innovation climate (Effect = .1900, 95% CI [.0823 to .2903]) compared to the moderate level of innovation climate (Effect = .3232, 95% CI [.2264 to .4155]) and compared to the low levels of innovation climate (Effect = .4565, 95% CI [.3210 to .5832]).

Table (4-19):**Conditional indirect effects of psychological safety on risk-taking.**

Mediator PS → Risk	Moderator Condition	Effect	BootSE	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Error competence	“Low” (-1 SD)	-.0491	.0545	-.1518	.0637
	“Moderate” (mean)	-.0314	.0387	-.1093	.0470
	“High” (+1 SD)	-.0137	.0551	-.1166	.0984
Learning from errors	“Low” (-1 SD)	-.1508	.0487	-.2637	-.0688
	“Moderate” (mean)	-.1573	.0578	-.2695	-.0452
	“High” (+1 SD)	-.1638	.0926	-.3370	.0281
Error risk taking	“Low” (-1 SD)	.4565	.0683	.3210	.5832
	“Moderate” (mean)	.3232	.0472	.2264	.4155
	“High” (+1 SD)	.1900	.0515	.0823	.2903
Error communication	“Low” (-1 SD)	.1196	.1618	-.2042	.4427
	“Moderate” (mean)	.0437	.1069	-.1704	.2521
	“High” (+1 SD)	-.0323	.1245	-.2763	.2090
Thinking about errors	“Low” (-1 SD)	.0795	.0649	-.0508	.2030
	“Moderate” (mean)	.0964	.0520	-.0139	.1944
	“High” (+1 SD)	.1134	.0726	-.0395	.2565

Overall, the moderated mediation model results provided partial support for hypotheses 5, 6, and 7. Results will have discussed in detail in chapter 5.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

1. Results discussion

- 1.1. Psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior
- 1.2. Psychological safety and error orientations
- 1.3. Error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior
- 1.4. The mediating role of error orientations
- 1.5. The moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior
- 1.6. The moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior
- 1.7. The moderated mediation relationships

2. Theoretical contributions

3. Practical implications

4. Limitations

5. Suggestions for future research

6. Conclusion

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to gain a better understanding of the role played by error orientations and innovation climate on the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors. To do this, the study establishes a moderated-mediation model in which innovation climate moderated the mediating effect of five positive error orientations (error competence, learning from errors, error risk-taking, error communication, and thinking about errors) on the relationship between psychological safety and each employee's entrepreneurial behavior (innovative behavior, proactive behavior, and work-related risk-taking). The results provided partial support for the moderated-mediation model, as well as it carried some surprises that could change the way researchers and practitioners think about the nature of the relationship between study variables.

This chapter provides a discussion of the results and shows the theoretical implications and practical implications that can be benefited from the results, concludes with a presentation of the limitations and suggestions for future research.

1. Results discussion:

1.1. Psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior:

The results of the study showed that psychological safety has a significant direct positive effect on employees' entrepreneurial behaviors (H1). Minutely, the study provides additional practical evidence converge with findings from previous literature confirmed that psychological safety through reducing interpersonal risks encourage taking work-related risks and promoting risky behavior like innovative behavior (Javed, Naqvi, Khan, Arjoon, & Tayyeb, 2017; Leung, Deng, Wang, & Zhou, 2015; Cao & Zhang, 2020; Sun & Huang, 2020) and proactive behavior (Chen et al., 2019). Overall, psychological safety is considered an effective factor to enhance employees' entrepreneurial behaviors at the individual level.

At the individual level, the employee evaluates the interpersonal consequences of his entrepreneurial behavior. Psychological safety positively affects this evaluation and makes the employee perceive that the gains of entrepreneurial behavior overwait the risks.

On the one hand, psychological safety increases the chances of employees' entrepreneurial behavior success, which mean gains for employee (financial or non-financial like gain respect). Because psychologically safe employees feel that their efforts, skills and talents are appreciated by their peers, which motivates them to explore novel ideas and directions. Also, employees feel safe to take the initiative, act proactively and promote their ideas. Additionally, employees can bring up problems and tough issues and ask for help, which is necessary during implementing entrepreneurial ideas. On the other hand, psychologically safe reduces risks of entrepreneurial behavior such as uncertainty and ambiguity about the success in early phases and risks of failure in late phases.

1.2. Psychological safety and error orientations:

Furthermore, as expected, the results showed the effective role of psychological safety in creating positive attitudes towards errors. According to hypothesis 2 results, psychological safety nurtures employees' sense of efficacy to cope with errors in the short term (error competence) and in the long term (learning from errors). As well as, when employees have a positive perception of the consequences of taking interpersonal risks in their work, they manifest more flexibility and openness toward errors, communicate about them and think about how to correct them and prevent them in the future.

Although previous studies do not test the relationship between psychological safety and error orientations, they paved the way theoretically for this relationship. For example, previous studies argued that psychological safety promotes speak up and report errors (Edmondson & Lei, 2014), help in responding constructively to errors (Hofmann & Mark, 2006), increase openness to discussing errors (Roussin et al., 2018) and promotes employees' learning from errors (Ye et al., 2019). Psychological safety helps build positive error orientation because it minimizes the negative consequences of errors, such as embarrassment or losing face. Thus, it makes employees exceed the negative impact of errors and focus on the constructive aspect of dealing with them.

In outsourcing companies, it is always preferred to detect and correct errors in the early phases before delivering the service to client firms. Psychological safety considers the very short-term interpersonal consequences one expects from committing an error and temporarily discounts the longer-term consequence (Edmondson, 2003). So, psychological

safety is very important in detecting and correcting errors early. For example, suppose a client firm orders to develop a certain software from an IT outsourcing company and an error occurs while building the software (e.g., wrong programming code). The employee who commits the error will focus on the potential immediate consequences of communicating his error or asking for help to correct it, such as being humiliated or scolded for committing this error. And he temporarily discounts the longer-term consequence of the error, such as failure to provide the required software to the customer. In this case, if the employee feels psychologically safe, he will communicate the error and ask for help. But if he does not feel psychologically safe, he would prefer to keep silent and cover up the error, which is harmful to the outsourcing companies in the long term and negatively affect customer satisfaction. That is why the results indicate that psychologically safe in outsourcing companies is more correlated to error communication than the other error orientations.

1.3. Error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior:

The results of the third hypothesis held expected and unexpected findings. As expected, error competence, learning from errors, error risk-taking, and error communication positively affect employees' innovative behavior. Error competence reflects the efficiency of dealing with errors in the short term while learning from errors reflects a long-term orientation dealing with errors (Rybowiak et al., 1999). Accordingly, both -coping with error in the short and long term- are significantly increase employees' innovative behavior. This result agrees with Hetzner, Gartmeier, Heid and Gruber (2011) and Nilsen and Ellström (2012), who found that both error competence and learning from errors are crucial for an individual's reflection at work, which helps translate experience into learning and provides opportunities for practice-based practice innovation.

The significant positive findings between error risk-taking and employees' innovative behavior integrated with Tjosvold and Yu (2007) findings that error risk-taking promotes managers' ratings of team innovation. Still, our result takes it to a different level of analysis: the individual level. Additionally, the researcher found that error communication is an important antecedent of innovative behavior. Previous studies generally confirmed that communication, knowledge-sharing, and voice behavior played a

constructive role in innovation (Guzman & Espejo, 2019; Liang, Zhang, Tian, & Tian, 2021; Sharif, Tongkachok, Akbar, Iqbal, & Lodhi, 2021). The current study results add to these previous studies by investigating a special type of communication and voice, which is communicating about errors. Error communication helps the error-doer himself and his peers or supervisors in knowing the frequent errors and their causes, thus innovating new ways to reduce these errors in the future.

Unexpectedly, the study found that thinking about errors negatively influences innovative behavior. This relationship could be interpreted through the nature of thinking about errors. Thinking about errors takes place after errors already occur, and it requires long and hard thinking about how errors happened, how to correct them and how to prevent them. This process consumes two important sources available for the employee: thinking (as a mental process) and time. Using limited time to think about the error rather than thinking about entrepreneurial activities (such as developing ideas and implementing them) may cause this opposite result. Additionally, thinking in errors as a mental process may make the employee's mind not clear and unprepared for creative thinking. Especially since errors are emotional events, thinking about them can even subconsciously increase negative emotions (e.g., shame, guilt, fear of losing face).

Hypothesis 3 also concluded that among the five error orientations, just error risk-taking and error communication significantly affect proactive behavior. This result may be due to the nature of error risk-taking and error communication, which involves personal interaction or openness to others. Meaning that error competence, learning from errors and thinking about errors do not need relations or connections to others. A person can cope with error in the short term or long term or think about his own errors by himself without including others at all. In contrast, error risk-taking and error communication cannot be isolated from others; both have a relational aspect. Previous studies highlighted the role of social relationships in promoting proactivity in organizations (e.g., Batistič, Černe, Kaše, & Zupic, 2016). So, the cause that only error risk-taking and error communication have a significant effect on proactive behavior may return to their relational nature. And for the same reason they have a significant positive effect on work-related risk-taking because

networking and social context are important factors that affect intrapreneurs as they must act within an organization with a certain climate and political field (Neessen et al., 2019).

Another unexpected finding of Hypothesis 3 is that learning from errors negatively affects risk-taking. Experiencing errors and learning from them may make employees more careful in dealing with risks, “once bitten twice shy”. Previous studies showed that, after a rare event experience, individuals tend to make more risk-averse choices than those who have not experienced those events (Said, Afzal, & Turner, 2015). Negative personal experiences are so powerful that they make individuals keep away from risk (Andersen, Hanspal, & Nielsen, 2019). Although traditional life-cycle models assume that risk preferences are time-invariant, recent research shows that risk-taking -by the same individuals- varies substantially over their life-cycle, as well as in response to shocks (Ayton, Bernile, Buccioli, & Zarri, 2020). Therefore, experiencing errors may present a negative event or shock that makes employees avoid taking risks. Particularly, learning from errors reflects long-term learning rather short-term.

However, it cannot be concluded that learning from errors causes individuals to totally avoid participating in entrepreneurial activities. The results indicate that learning from errors positively affects innovative behavior. Also, Wei and Hisrich (2016) found that learning from errors positively related to entrepreneurial opportunity identification and entrepreneurial decision-making. Thus, learning from errors makes people wiser and more thoughtful in dealing with innovations. Future studies must be carried out to understand this relationship, including other variables such as experience.

1.4. The mediating role of error orientations:

1.4.1. The mediating role of error orientations in the relationship between psychological safety and employees’ innovative behavior:

This study found that learning from errors, error risk-taking and error communication significantly and positively mediated the relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior (H4a). This finding provides a deeper understanding of the indirect relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior. Psychological safety by minimizing the interpersonal consequences of committing errors (Edmondson, 1999; Edmondson & Lei, 2014) encourages employees to

adopt positive attitudes towards errors embedded in any innovative activities (Jalonen, 2012); thus, employees would behave innovatively. In particular, psychological safety encourages learning from errors, error risk-taking, and error communication, which motivates individuals to participate in innovative behaviors without fear of interpersonal or error-related negative consequences. In other words, when employees feel psychologically safe, they can risk making mistakes to make achievements at work rather than doing nothing at all or sitting on one's behind, openly communicate their errors and learn from those errors. Thus, he would have more courage to behave innovatively despite the possibility of making errors.

In outsourcing companies, innovation is expected from the service provider because he is the partner who has the specialized knowledge of the service that he provides. To innovate, employees in outsourcing companies try novel ideas and new methods to do the work which increase the possibility of errors. In this stage, which errors are still a prospect, psychological safety helps employees have the courage to risk making some errors to achieve innovation. Further, when errors occur and become a reality, psychological safety helps detect errors early in the “provider firm” rather than covering up errors to be detected by customers in the “client firm” because employees feel safe to communicate errors and thus learn from them.

Nevertheless, the negative impact of thinking about errors on innovation continues with its role as a mediator between psychological safety and innovative behavior. The interpretation of this result is complex; despite the direct positive relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior, the indirect relationship via thinking about errors is negative. One way that psychological safety work is by encouraging positive interpersonal relationships in the workplace. Individuals want to maintain this strong working relationship with their colleagues and not spoil it with individual mistakes. Thus, after errors happen, they spend more time and effort thinking about the error to not repeat it, not because of fear of negative consequences but a desire to maintain strong working relationships.

In other words, the psychologically safe individual has been given the benefit of the doubt, then when he makes an error, he may feel that he has let down his colleagues or

was not up to their expectations, which may cause him to think or maybe overthink about errors. Thinking about the error consumes the mental energy of the employee and consumes his limited time, which are valuable resources that should be invested in innovative activities.

1.4.2. The mediating role of error orientations in the relationship between psychological safety and employees' proactive behavior:

Regarding the indirect relationship between psychological safety and proactive behavior, the study found that only error risk-taking and error communication mediate this relationship. Error risk-taking is related to taking the initiative (Rybowiak et al., 1999) because the employee initiated actions in order to achieve higher goals, regardless of the possibility of errors. This mechanism explains the mediating role of error risk-taking between psychological safety and proactive behavior. Psychological safety reduces the employee's perception of negative consequences of errors, which reduces his error concerns and makes him initiate actions ignoring the possibility of errors.

Furthermore, error communication also takes part in explaining the indirect relationship between psychological safety and proactive behavior. Psychological safety encourages interpersonal risk-taking and communication with people without fear of negative consequences—especially communication about errors. Compared to other types of communication in the organization, communicating about personal errors has more expected negative effects on self-image or status. Hence, people do not voluntarily speak out about their mistakes and errors unless they feel safe from such negative effects. When employees feel psychologically safe, they first take the initiative to speak openly about their errors to improve themselves and then initiate work-related issues to improve their work.

In line with the result of the third hypothesis (H3b) that there is no evidence for the relationship between error competence, learning from errors, thinking about errors and proactive behavior. There is no evidence for the mediating role of those three variables between psychological safety and proactive behavior.

1.4.3. The mediating role of error orientations in the relationship between psychological safety and employees' risk-taking:

Hypothesis 4c concluded that only error risk-taking plays a significant positive mediating role in the relationship between psychological safety and work-related risk-taking among the five error orientations. This result helps us understand the relationship between three types of risks in the workplace: interpersonal risk, error risk and work-related risk. As expected, psychological safety encourages interpersonal risk-taking, which encourages error risk-taking, which encourages work-related risk-taking.

However, learning from errors has a negative mediating role in the relationship between psychological safety and work-related risk-taking; this may also be due to the experiences related to errors. For example, risk-takers act and then asks for approval from top management. But after experiencing errors and learning, they may replace this habit and ask for approval before acting, which means less risk-taking.

In general, through the results of the fourth hypothesis, it can be said that error risk-taking is the best explanation of the indirect relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors. Because it positively mediates the relationship between psychological safety and all entrepreneurial behaviors – innovative, proactive and risk-taking behavior. In other words, when an employee feels psychologically safe, he can risk making mistakes to make achievements at work. Thus, he would have more courage to take work-related risks and behave innovatively and proactively despite the possibility of making errors.

1.5. The moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between psychological safety and employees' entrepreneurial behavior:

Contrary to expected, this study found no evidence for the moderating effect of innovation climate on the relationship between psychological safety, innovative behavior and proactive behavior. This finding was initially surprising, as innovation climate has shown a significant moderating effect on innovation outcomes in previous research (Newman et al., 2020). However, a possible explanation for the observed relationships in this study may be that the effects of innovation climate were dramatically overshadowed

by the magnitude influence of error orientation as a mediator, especially with the relatively too many variables in the hypothesized model (10 variables).

Still, Hypothesis 5 found that the innovation climate has a positive significant moderation effect on the relationship between psychological safety and risk-taking. When employees perceive that the organization supports creativity and provide them with the necessary resource to work on their ideas, the relationship between psychological safety and risk-taking becomes stronger. The innovation climate accelerates the transformation of interpersonal risk-taking into work-related risk-taking. This finding agrees with previous studies, as innovation climate enhanced risk propensity (Magni, Palmi, & Salvemini, 2018; Menzel, Aaltio, & Ulijn, 2007; Oke, Prajogo, & Jayaram, 2013).

Employees form their innovation climate perspective according to the environmental factors such as policies, processes, and managerial behavior (Zhou & Zhang, 2017). For example, employees evaluate the managerial reaction to risk-taking to know if it is a preferred behavior in the organization or not. If risk-taking is preferred, employees would have an optimistic expectation about the potential consequences of taking risks and perceive a high level of innovation climate. In the same context, psychologically safe employees perceive that their peers would tolerate taking interpersonal risks. Thus, the interaction between risk-taking support by the organization (innovation climate) and risk-taking support at the interpersonal level (psychological safety) would motivate the employees to take work-related risks.

1.6. The moderating role of innovation climate in the relationship between error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behavior:

The results of the sixth hypothesis showed that innovation climate positively and significantly moderated the relationship between error risk-taking and innovative behavior - among the five-error orientations. Meaning that the employees' flexibility and openness towards errors produce more innovative behavior when he feels supported by the organization. This is due to the role innovation climate plays in encouraging risk-taking (Oke et al., 2013a), risks related to errors in this case, which encourages employees to engage in innovative behavior. Likewise, innovation climate positively and significantly

moderated the relationship between error risk taking and proactive behavior through the same effect.

Interestingly, innovation climate negatively moderates the relationship between error competence, error communication and proactive behavior. Error competence reflects that employees have a sense of efficacy to cope with errors in the short term (Rybowiak et al., 1999). When employees perceive innovation climate as supportive in which they have time and resources to work on their errors individually, employees may prefer not to engage in proactive behavior, which has a social and relational consideration (Parker, Wang, & Liao, 2019). In other words, why does the employee take the initiative to speak about his errors or behave proactively in an error situation if he can handle his error individually. In line with that, innovation climate also weakens the positive relationship between error communication and proactive behavior. So that, when employees have active knowledge enables them to recover immediately from errors and perceived high innovation climate, he communicates less about their errors and shows less proactive behavior because he can fix his mistakes by himself.

Another unexpected finding of hypothesis six is that innovation climate negatively affects the relationship between error risk-taking and work-related risk-taking. The relationship is still positive but weaker. This finding was surprising, as innovation climate encourages risk-taking (Oke et al., 2013), so the relationship should be stronger. But, considering the innovation climate effect on risk, the researcher interpretant this as the too much effect of a good thing, as in such a risk-free environment, employees may feel sluggish at work. Hence, no need to take risks at work. Referring to the finding of Bhandari and Hallowell (2022) as they found a negative relationship between workers feeling physically safe on a construction site and risk-taking decisions in the workplace. Although Bhandari and Hallowell's study differs from the field of our current study, it indicates the necessary further investigation about how much risk encouragement leads to positive outcomes.

1.7. The moderated mediation relationships:

In line with the results of the fourth hypothesis (error risk-taking is the best mediator to explain the relationship between psychological safety and employees'

entrepreneurial behaviors) and the results of the sixth hypothesis (innovation climate moderates the relationship between error risk-taking and all the entrepreneurial behaviors). The results of moderated mediation indexes show that innovation climate moderates the mediating effect of psychological safety on employees' entrepreneurial behavior via error risk-taking only - among the five error orientations. No support was found for moderated mediation in the relationship between psychological safety and employee's entrepreneurial behavior via error competence, learning from errors, error communication or thinking about errors.

Results showed that when innovation climate is high, the indirect effect of psychological safety on employees' innovation and proactive behaviors via error risk-taking is stronger. This result agreed with the previous studies in using risk reduction as a mechanism to explain why psychological safety effect employees' innovation and proactive behaviors. When an employee feels psychologically safe, he would have more courage to behave innovatively and proactively despite the possibility of making errors. This relationship would be stronger when employees perceived that the organizational climate supports creativity.

2. Theoretical contributions:

The study makes multiple contributions to the entrepreneurial behaviors literature in several ways. First, this study responds to calls urging further work on intrapreneurship at the individual level (Blanka, 2019; Neessen et al., 2019) and how to improve employee acceptance of risk and behave innovatively (AlEssa & Durugbo, 2021). The present research suggests interpersonal risk-taking as an important antecedent of employees' entrepreneurial behaviors. Findings are congruent with the existing findings on the direct effect of psychological safety on innovative work behavior (Cao & Zhang, 2020) and proactive behavior (Chen et al., 2019). However, the direct relationship between psychological safety and error orientations is a new contribution to the literature (except learning from errors). Furthermore, although errors are expected in any entrepreneurial work, especially at the individual level, this is the first study to investigate the relationship between positive error orientations and employees' entrepreneurial behaviors.

Second, through the mediation hypothesis, this study finds that error risk-taking is the best mediator to explain the indirect relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behaviors. Psychological safety has been conceived as an important factor that reduces interpersonal risks in the workplace (Frazier et al., 2017; Newman et al., 2017b); thus, it is related directly to entrepreneurial behavior. Our study moves a step forward and contributes to the literature by identifying error risk-taking as an important mediating mechanism underlying psychological safety- entrepreneurial behavior relationship at the individual level. In other words, when an employee feels psychologically safe, he can risk making mistakes to make achievements at work rather than not doing nothing at all or sit on one's behind. Thus, he would have more courage to behave entrepreneurially despite the possibility of making errors.

Third, the research theorizes and test the moderating role of innovation climate on the indirect effects of psychological safety on innovative behavior via error orientations. Our results showed that when innovation climate is high, the indirect effect of psychological safety on innovative and proactive behavior via error risk-taking is stronger. This finding aligns with the prior findings that innovation climate work as a supportive moderation in influencing employees' innovative behavior (Newman et al., 2020).

Fourth, the results have come up with some unexpected findings that could change the researchers' view of the relationship between these variables. The results indicated that thinking about errors may deter innovative behavior. And that a risk-free environment may negatively affect employee risk-taking. We hope that future studies will confirm these results and add other variables to explain them.

Finally, the study validated the direct relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior in a non-western context and added new insights into the relationships that had not been tested in the literature earlier. By testing the conceptual model in the Egyptian setting, the study provides new evidence of the relationships between psychological safety and innovation. In addition, the study gives a new insight into understanding the relationship between psychological safety and other entrepreneurial behaviors (proactive behavior and risk-taking) by testing new variables that have not been previously studied (error orientation and innovation climate).

3. Practical implications:

The current research is significant for practitioners to understand and stimulate employees' entrepreneurial behavior. Results highlight the importance of psychological safety in shaping employees' attitudes toward error risks and then in promoting employees' entrepreneurial behavior. So, building a psychologically safe work environment is very merit.

Previous studies suggested some strategies that assist organizations in providing a psychologically safe environment. For example, firms should encourage their talented employees to share their valuable knowledge in the form of ideas, insights, know-how, and experiences. This can be done through regular meetings, brainstorming sessions, the organization's database, or facilitating communities of practice. Additionally, organizations should facilitate a learning environment for continuous employee development through organizing workshops, conferences, seminars, and management development programs (Tiwari & Lenka, 2016). Recent studies suggest targeted training - that facilitates building a personal connection and an awareness of interdependence among employees- to increase psychological safety (Dusenberry & Robinson, 2020).

Furthermore, management should exert a modeling role in errors situations. For example, giving an employee the benefit of the doubt when he commits an error will enhance a sense of psychological safety and give flexibility and openness toward errors, making the employee abandon extreme caution and be more open to innovation. But be careful, the study does not advocate the acceptance of errors per se but the possibility of errors. One explanation of error risk-taking is that it is a reference to a high achievement-oriented attitude (Rybowiak et al., 1999). In this perspective, managers should focus on the required achievement in dealing with those employees, not on the errors that could happen while working on reaching this achievement.

In the same context, management should use error management training instead of error avoidant training. Participants are given opportunities to make errors during training and are encouraged to use these errors as a learning device (Keith & Frese, 2005). This way, the organization would be able to manage errors to increase positive consequences, such as long-term learning, performance, and innovation (Frese & Keith, 2015). The

present findings may also be relevant in such training projects as instructors can use psychological safety to enable trainees to gain confidence in their error-coping competence and perform more effectively, thereby benefiting both the individual and the organization.

Moreover, the moderated mediation result suggests the significance of creating innovation climate. According to the findings, when the employees' perceptions about the innovation climate are high, the prementioned relationships between psychological safety, error risk-taking, innovative behavior and proactive behavior become stronger. Organizational orders have to be more flexible to allow individual differences between employees. Also, organizations should devote resources and time to innovation. According to our measurement of innovation climate as a psychological climate, the organization should formulate not only formal practices that support creativity but also send clear and consistent signals to employees, emphasizing the organization's support for creativity.

Finally, the results also carry some caveats for management as it should not overstate the risk reduction in the workplace. A risk-free environment may not motivate the employee to take risks, but rather slacken and give in to easy work. Likewise, management should deal with error thinking with caution. The goal of thinking about errors is to draw lessons for the future and learning, not to make the employee remember the negative feelings accompanying the error, such as guilt or remorse. Thinking about error should be an official and organizational activity, not an individual act. So thinking about the error will take from regular work time, not idea development time. For example, asking employees to write a report explaining errors' causes, correction ways, and prevention suggestions will determine the time of thinking about errors. This time will end by reporting admission. Also, it will allow free communication about errors with management and facilitate innovative suggestions from employees about preventing similar errors.

4. Limitations:

Our findings should be interpreted with respect to some limitations. First, the study uses a cross-sectional design that reflects correlational rather than causal relationships. Future research could adopt stronger study designs to enable manipulating the study variables and confirm the causal inferences. Likewise, the data on the study variables were self-reported and collected at a single point in time. Although the researcher made every

attempt to avoid concerns of common method variance, its possibility cannot be altogether discounted. Second, data were collected during the COVID-19 crisis, which may pose some risks to employees. Therefore, this study should have measured and controlled COVID-19 related risks. Particularly, the study is interested in how to minimize risks (interpersonal and error risks) to motivate employees' entrepreneurial behaviors. In the same context, the research used one type of risk (error risks) to explain the relationship between psychological safety and entrepreneurial behavior. Future researchers could examine other types of risks that may affect this relationship, like employees' financial risks. Since the employee's financial situation is at risk, he will be more conservative in his interpersonal relationships and more afraid of making mistakes. Therefore, studying or controlling financial risks will reveal more about the nature of the relationship between psychological safety and innovative behavior. Third, our measure of error orientations was toward errors in general rather than capture specifically entrepreneurship-related errors. The future researcher should distinguish between errors that occur in daily work and errors that occur during entrepreneurial activities.

5. Suggestions for Future Research:

It is noted from the results the significance and strength of the relationship between psychological safety and all error orientations, in contrast to the relationship between error orientations and entrepreneurial behavior, which is not as strong. Therefore, future studies may test the assumed model but with different outcomes. For example, at the individual level, the employee's sense of psychological safety with a positive orientation toward errors may lead to employee psychological well-being; this relationship has not yet been investigated. Or at the organizational level, psychological safety facilitates learning behavior, and when employees can use errors as a learning source, this would lead to long-term organizational learning.

Second, the topic of intrapreneurship is still a fertile field for research. For the purposes of this research, the present study used only three behaviors to express the entrepreneurial behavior at the individual level, while (Neessen et al., 2019) refer to other entrepreneurial behaviors such as opportunity recognition, exploitation and networking. Gawke, Gorgievski, and Bakker (2019) also presented another measurement relay on the

basis of employee activities that contribute to firm-level intrapreneurship (venture behavior and strategic renewal behavior). Future research may test and compare these different views and measurements of intrapreneurship to deepen our understanding of this phenomenon. Or future scholars may suggest a model for how intrapreneurship is integrated at different levels, from the organizational level to the individual level.

Finally, the results showed some unexpected findings that require further investigation. For example, the role of emotions reacted to errors in the relationship between thinking about errors and innovative behavior. Moreover, social relationships can be used to differentiate between error orientations, which of them need strong social relationships (such as error communication) and which ones do not need strong social relationships (such as thinking about errors). Thus, we will know how to influence it and understand its relationships with other variables, such as proactive behavior in the case of the current research. Furthermore, future studies should study the appropriate amount of risks tolerance and whether there is a negative effect of a risk-free context.

6. Conclusion:

The purpose of the present study was to understand the explanatory role of error orientations and the conditional role of innovation climate in the relationship between psychological safety and employees' intrapreneurial behavior. This study found evidence that psychological safety positively affects error orientations and entrepreneurial behaviors, while error risk-taking is the best explanatory orientation to explain the positive effect of psychological safety on intrapreneurial behaviors. Further, innovation climate moderates the mediating effect of psychological safety on employees' entrepreneurial behavior via error risk-taking.

Though, the study also found some unexpected results, which are discussed in detail in this chapter, as well as its interpretations and recommendations. Future research should expand on this avenue depending on our results (expected and unexpected). As the organizational landscape continues to change and the nature of work arrangements evolves, organizations, managers, and employees benefit from a better understanding of how to improve entrepreneurial behaviors at the individual level.

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APPENDICES

Appendix (A)

**The permission to conduct
the study from the Central
Agency for Public
Mobilization and Statistics.**

جمهورية مصر العربية

الجهاز المركزي للتعينة العامة والإحصاء

قرار رئيس الجهاز المركزي للتعينة العامة والإحصاء

بالتفويض رقم (٧٢٦) لسنة ٢٠٢١

في شأن قيام الباحث / أحمد محمد محمود السيد - المسجل لدرجة دكتوراه الفلسفة في إدارة الأعمال / كلية التجارة جامعة المنصورة - بإجراء دراسة ميدانية بعنوان: (دور التوجه بالخطأ ومناخ الإبداع في العلاقة بين الأمان النفسي والسلوك الريادي للموظف - بالتطبيق على العاملين بشركات تعهيد الأعمال بالقرية الذكية بمصر).

رئيس الجهاز

- بعد الإطلاع على القرار الجمهوري رقم (٢٩١٥) لسنة ١٩٦٤ بشأن إنشاء الجهاز المركزي للتعينة العامة والإحصاء.
- وعلى قرار رئيس الجهاز رقم (٢٣١) لسنة ١٩٦٨ في شأن إجراء الإحصاءات والتعدادات والاستفتاءات والاستقصاءات.
- وعلى قرار رئيس الجهاز رقم (١٣١٤) لسنة ٢٠٠٧ بشأن التفويض في بعض الاختصاصات.
- وعلى كتاب كلية التجارة - جامعة المنصورة - الوارد للجهاز في ٢٨/٦/٢٠٢١ .

ق ر ر

- مادة ١: يقوم الباحث / أحمد محمد محمود السيد - المسجل لدرجة دكتوراه الفلسفة في إدارة الأعمال / كلية التجارة جامعة المنصورة - بإجراء الدراسة الميدانية المشار إليها عالية.
- مادة ٢: تجرى الدراسة علي عينة حجمها (٣٨٤) ثلاثمائة وأربعة وثمانون مفردة من السادة / العاملين بشركات تعهيد الأعمال بالقرية الذكية وذلك بمحافظة الجيزة .
- مادة ٣: تجمع البيانات اللازمة لهذه الدراسة بموجب الاستمارة المعدة لذلك وعدد صفحاتها خمس صفحات والمُعتمده كل صفحة منها بخاتم الجهاز المركزي للتعينة العامة والإحصاء .
- مادة ٤: تقوم الشركات المستهدفة - وتحت إشراف إدارة الأمن بكل منها - بتيسير إجراء هذه الدراسة الميدانية ومراعاة الضوابط الخاصة بتقييم درجة سرية البيانات والمعلومات المتداولة مسبقاً بمعرفة كل جهة طبقاً لما جاء بخطة الأمن بها .
- مادة ٥: يراعي موافقة مفردات العينة - وسرية البيانات الفردية طبقاً لقانون الجهاز رقم (٣٥) لسنة ١٩٦٠ والمُعدل بالقانون رقم (٢٨) لسنة ١٩٨٢ وعدم استخدام البيانات التي يتم جمعها لأغراض أخرى غير أغراض هذه الدراسة .
- مادة ٦: يجري العمل الميداني خلال ثلاثة أشهر من تاريخ صدور هذا القرار.
- مادة ٧: يوافق الجهاز المركزي للتعينة العامة والإحصاء بنسخة من النتائج النهائية لهذه الدراسة .
- مادة ٨: ينفذ هذا القرار من تاريخ صدوره .
- صدر في: ٤ / ٧ / ٢٠٢١ .

رئيس الإدارة المركزية

لشئون مكتب رئيس الجهاز

Appendix (B)
Study Questionnaire

أولاً: البيانات الديموجرافية:

(1) النوع

- ذكر أنثى

(2) العمر

- أقل من 25 سنة من 35 سنة حتي أقل من 40 سنة
 من 25 سنة حتي أقل من 30 سنة من 40 سنة حتي أقل من 45 سنة
 من 30 سنة حتي أقل من 35 سنة أكثر من 45 سنة

(3) المستوى التعليمي

- شهادة جامعية أولى دكتوراه
 ماجستير

(4) عدد سنوات الخبرة في مجال العمل

- أقل من 5 سنوات من 15 سنة حتي أقل من 20 سنة
 من 5 سنوات حتي أقل من 10 سنوات أكثر من 20 سنة
 من 10 سنوات حتي أقل من 15 سنة

(5) عدد سنوات الخبرة في الوظيفة الحالية

- أقل من 5 سنوات من 5 سنوات حتي أقل من 10 سنوات
 من 10 سنوات حتي أقل من 15 سنة من 15 سنة حتي أقل من 20 سنة
 أكثر من 20 سنة

ثانياً: يرجى قراءة العبارات التالية جيداً ثم حدد الإختيار الذي يعبر عن درجة موافقتك

موافق تماماً	موافق	محايد	غير موافق	غير موافق تماماً	العبارة
5	4	3	2	1	(1) يلتبس زملائي لي العذر إذا أخطأت.
5	4	3	2	1	(2) يستطيع العاملون في المنظمة إثارة المشكلات والقضايا الحرجة دون خوف.
5	4	3	2	1	(3) لا يرفض زملائي التعامل معي، حتى وإن كان هناك إختلافات شخصية.
5	4	3	2	1	(4) أستطيع تحمل قدر من المخاطر في هذه المنظمة.
5	4	3	2	1	(5) يسهل علي طلب المساعدة من زملائي في المنظمة.
5	4	3	2	1	(6) لا يعتمد أحد من زملائي التقليل من جهودي في العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(7) لا أتردد في إفادة زملائي في العمل بمهاراتي ومواهي.
5	4	3	2	1	(8) أعرف كيف أصحح أخطائي في العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(9) أصحح أخطائي في العمل فوراً دون تأخر.
5	4	3	2	1	(10) أستطيع تصحيح الأخطاء المعتادة في العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(11) لا أحييد عن الهدف برغم أنني قد أخطئ.
5	4	3	2	1	(12) أستفيد من أخطائي الشخصية في تحسين عملي.
5	4	3	2	1	(13) أستفيد من أخطاء الآخرين في تحسين عملي.
5	4	3	2	1	(14) قد تُمدني الأخطاء بمعلومات تساعدني في أداء عملي لاحقاً.
5	4	3	2	1	(15) أحاول تحسين مهاراتي لمنع تكرار أخطائي السابقة في العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(16) تحقيق إنجازات في العمل قد يقترن بمخاطر ارتكاب بعض الأخطاء.
5	4	3	2	1	(17) أخاطر بإحتمال ارتكاب بعض الأخطاء، ولا أكثر من طرح الأسئلة عن العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(18) أتحمل مسؤولية حدوث بعض الأخطاء من أجل سير العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(19) عند التعرض لمواقف جديدة، أفضل التجربة والخطأ عن عدم التصرف مطلقاً.
5	4	3	2	1	(20) إذا أخطأت في العمل، فإنني أنصح زملائي بتجنب تكرار نفس الخطأ.

موافق تماماً	موافق	محايد	غير موافق	غير موافق تماماً	العبارة
5	4	3	2	1	(21) إذا لم أتمكن من تصحيح الخطأ بنفسني، فإنني أطلب المساعدة من زملائي.
5	4	3	2	1	(22) إذا لم أتمكن من تصحيح خطأ ما، يمكنني الإعتماد علي زملائي في تصحيحه.
5	4	3	2	1	(23) عندما أخطئ في عمل ما، فإنني أسأل زملائي عن طريقة أداء هذا العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(24) أستفيد من مناقشة أخطائي مع الزملاء.
5	4	3	2	1	(25) بعد حدوث خطأ ما فإنني أفكر في أسباب حدوثه.
5	4	3	2	1	(26) غالباً ما أفكر "كيف يمكنني منع حدوث الأخطاء في العمل".
5	4	3	2	1	(27) أفكر في الأخطاء التي تحدث في العمل بتأني.
5	4	3	2	1	(28) بعد حدوث خطأ ما، أفكر كثيراً وبجدية كيف أصححه.
5	4	3	2	1	(29) أقدم إقتراحات لتحسين المنتجات والخدمات الحالية.
5	4	3	2	1	(30) اقترح أفكار لتحسين ممارسات العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(31) أحاول اكتساب معلومات جديدة.
5	4	3	2	1	(32) أشارك في تقديم منتجات وخدمات جديدة.
5	4	3	2	1	(33) أحاول جذب عملاء جدد.
5	4	3	2	1	(34) أعمل علي تحسين تنظيم العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(35) أحاول تحسين إجراءات العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(36) أجرب أساليب عمل جديدة أكثر فاعلية.
5	4	3	2	1	(37) أحاول تنفيذ حلول لمشاكل المنظمة الملحة.
5	4	3	2	1	(38) أحاول تقديم أساليب جديدة لتحسين كفاءة العمل.
5	4	3	2	1	(39) أستمتع بالمهام الغامضة التي بها قدر من التحدي.
5	4	3	2	1	(40) مستعد لتحمل مخاطرة كبيرة إذا كانت المكافآت المحتملة عالية.
5	4	3	2	1	(41) اثناء العمل، أقوم بالتصرف المناسب أولاً ثم أخبر الإدارة العليا لاحقاً.
5	4	3	2	1	(42) المهمة الرئيسية لنا في المنظمة هي إتباع أوامر الإدارة.

العبارة					غير موافق تماماً	غير موافق	محايد	موافق	موافق تماماً
5	4	3	2	1	(43) يمكن لأي شخص التعرض لكثير من المتاعب لكونه مختلفاً.				
5	4	3	2	1	(44) تُفضل المنظمة استمرار الوضع الحالي أكثر من التغيير.				
5	4	3	2	1	(45) تُخصص المنظمة موارد كافية لدعم الابتكار.				
5	4	3	2	1	(46) يتوفر الوقت الكافي للعمل علي الأفكار الإبداعية .				
5	4	3	2	1	(47) تُخصص المنظمة وقتاً لمتابعة الأفكار الإبداعية خلال يوم العمل.				

خالص شكري وتقديري
الباحث